

Reference	Country: Study design	Aim	Population
<p>Aalto-Korte, K., Alanko, K., Kuuliala, O., & Jolanki, R. (2007). Methacrylate and acrylate allergy in dental personnel. <i>Contact Dermatitis</i>, 57(5), 324-330. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0536.2007.01237.x</p>	<p>Finland: Retrospective observational</p>	<p>Analyse patch test reactivity to 36 acrylic monomers in dental personnel</p>	<p>Dental personnel</p>
<p>Aalto-Korte, K., Henriks-Eckerman, M. L., Kuuliala, O., & Jolanki, R. (2010). Occupational methacrylate and acrylate allergy – cross-reactions and possible screening allergens. <i>Contact Dermatitis</i>, 63(6), 301-312. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0536.2010.01760.x</p>	<p>Finland: Retrospective observational</p>	<p>Analyse patterns concomitant patch test reactions to acrylic monomers in relation to exposure, and suggest possible screening allergens</p>	<p>HCP, patients and other professions/general population: Adults</p>
<p>Aalto-Korte, K., Jungewelter, S., Henriks-Eckerman, M.-L., Kuuliala, O., & Jolanki, R. (2009). Contact allergy to epoxy (meth)acrylates. <i>Contact dermatitis</i>, 61(1), 9-21. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0536.2009.01574.x</p>	<p>Finland: Retrospective observational: Case-control</p>	<p>Analyse patterns concomitant allergic reactions to 5 epoxy (meth)acrylates in relation to exposure</p>	<p>24 assumed adult (3 professionals related to dentistry)</p>
<p>Abass, K., Huusko, A., Knutsen, H. K., Nieminen, P., Myllynen, P., Meltzer, H. M., Vahakangas, K., & Rautio, A. (2018). Quantitative estimation of Hg intake by toxicokinetic modelling based on total Hg levels in humans. <i>Environment international</i>, 114, 1-11. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.02.028</p>	<p>Norway: Retrospective observational</p>	<p>Used three linear toxicokinetic models to describe fate of methyl Hg, inorganic Hg, and metallic Hg in body to estimate Hg daily intake via total Hg blood concentrations. Compared modelling results to detailed semiquantitative food frequency questionnaire of Norwegian Fish and Game Study, focused on dietary Hg exposure</p>	<p>Adult ≥18yrs</p>

<p>Ahlgren, C., Isaksson, M., Möller, H., Axéll, T., Liedholm, R., & Bruze, M. (2013). The necessity of a test reading after 1 week to detect late positive patch test reactions in patients with oral lichen lesions. <i>Clinical Oral Investigations</i>, 18(5), 1525-1531. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784-013-1122-0</p>	<p>Sweden: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Analyse frequency of late positive reactions to potential allergens in OLL patients</p>	<p>Patients: Adults aged 21 or above (Mean 60.0yrs, range 32-83). Suspected OLL</p>
<p>Albakry, M. (2021). Alveolar Bone Loss, Plaque Index, and Gingival Index among Non-Diabetics Treated with Class II Amalgam Restorations for Different Service Lives. <i>American Journal Of Biomedical Science & Research</i>, 13(6), 603-610. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.34297/ajbsr.2021.13.001924</p>	<p>Saudi Arabia: Cross sectional study with comparison group</p>	<p>Evaluate influence of different service lives of class II amalgam restorations on periodontal health among patients without diabetes</p>	<p>Patients: Adults 45-60yrs</p>
<p>Albakry, M. (2021). The Effect of the Different Service Lives of Class II Amalgam Restorations on Periodontal Health among Type 2 Diabetes Patients. <i>International Journal Of Dentistry And Oral Health</i>, 7(6). https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.16966/2378-7090.374</p>	<p>See Albakry 2021:</p>	<p>Evaluate effect of different service lives of class II amalgam restorations on periodontal health among type 2 diabetes patients</p>	<p>See Albakry 2021</p>

<p>Al-Saleh I, Coskun S, Mashhour A, Shinwari N, El-Doush I, Billedo G, Jaroudi K, Al-Shahrani A, Al-Kabra M, El Din Mohamed G. Exposure to heavy metals (lead, cadmium and mercury) and its effect on the outcome of in-vitro fertilization treatment. <i>Int J Hyg Environ Health</i>. 2008 Oct;211(5-6):560-79. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2007.09.005. Epub 2007 Dec 21. PMID: 18160343.</p>	<p>Saudi Arabia: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Evaluate extent of mercury (Hg) exposure and predict its sources in the healthy Saudi population</p>	<p>Maternal exposure: Mothers and infants (3-12 months)</p>
<p>Al-Saleh, I. (2020). Reference values for heavy metals in the urine and blood of Saudi women derived from two human biomonitoring studies. <i>International journal of hygiene and environmental health</i>, 225, 113473. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113473</p>	<p>Saudi Arabia: Secondary analysis of cross sectional study</p>	<p>(1) Calculate RV95 for Hg, Cd and lead in blood and urine from Saudi women based on 95th %ile of metal and corresponding 95% CI, (2) compare with RV95s established in other countries</p>	<p>Women (16-50yrs)</p>
<p>Al-Saleh, I., & Al-Sedairi Al, A. (2011). Hg (Hg) burden in children: the impact of DA. <i>The Science of the total environment</i>, 409(16), 3003-3015. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.04.047</p>	<p>Saudi Arabia: Cross sectional with comparison group</p>	<p>Estimate Hg body burden and its association with DA fillings in children living in Taif City</p>	<p>Child patient (5-15yrs)</p>

<p>Al-Saleh, I., Abduljabbar, M., Al-Rouqi, R., Eltabache, C., Al-Rajudi, T., Elkhatib, R., & Nester, M. (2015). The extent of Hg (Hg) exposure among Saudi mothers and their respective infants. <i>Environmental monitoring and assessment</i>, 187(11), 678. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10661-015-4858-y</p>	<p>Saudi Arabia: Cross sectional study</p>	<p>Evaluate impact of Hg exposure on infant neurodevelopment. Part of project that (1) determined extent of Hg exposure in Saudi mothers and respective infants, (2) evaluated various forms Hg exposure and predictive validity for assessment of accurate biological monitoring by measuring Hg levels in various biological samples e.g. maternal blood, breast milk, urine, and hair and infant urine and hair, and (3) identified potential predictors of Hg exposure using exposure assessment questionnaires</p>	<p>Maternal exposure (17-48yrs);</p>
<p>Al-Saleh, I., Al-Sedairi Al, a., & Elkhatib, R. (2012). Effect of Hg (Hg) DA fillings on renal and oxidative stress biomarkers in children. <i>The Science of the total environment</i>, 431, 188-196. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2012.05.036</p>	<p>Saudi Arabia: Cross sectional with comparison group</p>	<p>Examine effect of Hg associated with DA fillings on biomarkers of renal and oxidative stress in children</p>	<p>Child patient (5-15.5yrs)</p>
<p>Anglen, J., Gruninger Stephen, E., Chou, H.-N., Weuve, J., Turyk Mary, E., Freels, S., & Stayner Leslie, T. (2015). Occupational mercury exposure in association with prevalence of multiple sclerosis and tremor among US dentists. <i>Journal of the American Dental Association</i> (1939), 146(9), 659-668.e651. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.adaaj.2015.05.016</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional with comparison group</p>	<p>Evaluate association of occupational Hg0 exposure with multiple sclerosis (MS) and tremor</p>	<p>HCP: Dentists</p>

<p>Baek, H.-J., Kim, E.-K., Lee Sang, G., Jeong, S.-H., Sakong, J., Merchant Anwar, T., Im, S.-U., Song, K.-B., & Choi, Y.-H. (2016). DA exposure can elevate U-Hg concentrations in children. <i>International dental journal</i>, 66(3), 136-143. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/idj.12214</p>	<p>Korea: Prospective longitudinal</p>	<p>Evaluate relationship between DA exposure and U-Hg concentrations in children</p>	<p>Children (8-11yrs)</p>
<p>Barregard, L., Fabricius-Lagging, E., Lundh, T., Molne, J., Wallin, M., Olausson, M., Modigh, C., & Sallsten, G. (2010). Cadmium, mercury, and lead in kidney cortex of living kidney donors: Impact of different exposure sources. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 110(1), 47-54. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2009.10.009</p>	<p>Sweden: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Determine kidney concentrations of Cd, Hg, and Pb in living kidney donors, and assess associations with common exposure sources and background factors</p>	<p>Determine kidney concentrations of Cd, Hg, and Pb in living kidney donors, and assess associations with common exposure sources and background factors</p>
<p>Bartel-Steinbach, M., Lermen, D., Gwinner, F., Schafer, M., Goen, T., Conrad, A., Weber, T., von Briesen, H., & Kolossa-Gehring, M. (2022). Long-term monitoring of Hg in young German adults: Time trend analyses from the German Environmental Specimen Bank, 1995-2018. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 207, 112592. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.112592</p>	<p>Germany : Retrospective observational</p>	<p>Evaluate time trends of Hg exposure in Germany and the success of mitigation measures implemented up to now by analysing the data set of the German ESB collected from 1995 to 2018. Moreover, influencing factors of Hg exposure are investigated to provide further insight into human Hg exposure and possibilities of its reduction</p>	<p>Adults (20-29yrs)</p>
<p>Bashore CJ, Geer LA, He X, et al. Maternal Hg exposure, season of conception and adverse birth outcomes in an urban immigrant community in Brooklyn, New York, U.S.A. <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i> 2014;11:8414–42. [PubMed: 25153469]</p>	<p>USA: Prospective cohort</p>	<p>Examine association prenatal Hg exposure and season of conception with PTB and LBW in a high-risk population of African-American, Caribbean and West Indian women in an urban immigrant community in Brooklyn, New York. Examined association of prenatal Hg exposure with neonate anthropometric data</p>	<p>Maternal exposure-children</p>

<p>Becker, K., Schroeter-Kermani, C., Seiwert, M., Ruther, M., Conrad, A., Schulz, C., Wilhelm, M., Wittsiepe, J., Günsel, A., Dobler, L., & Kolossa-Gehring, M. (2013). German health-related environmental monitoring: assessing time trends of the general population's exposure to heavy metals. <i>International journal of hygiene and environmental health</i>, 216(3), 250-254. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2013.01.002</p>	<p>Germany : Retrospective observational</p>	<p>Analyse and document extent, distribution and determinants of exposure to environmental pollutants of German general population</p>	<p>Adults/Child</p>
<p>Bergdahl Ingvar, A., Ahlqwist, M., Barregard, L., Bjorkelund, C., Blomstrand, A., Skerfving, S., Sundh, V., Wennberg, M., & Lissner, L. (2013). Hg in serum predicts low risk of death and myocardial infarction in Gothenburg women. <i>International archives of occupational and environmental health</i>, 86(1), 71-77. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00420-012-0746-8</p>	<p>Sweden: Prospective longitudinal</p>	<p>Assess association between serum Hg and risk of cardiovascular disease in a prospective population-based cohort, with attention to the roles of dental health and fish consumption</p>	<p>Women (38-60yrs)</p>
<p>Berge, T. L. L., Lygre, G. B., Jonsson, B. A. G., Lindh, C. H., & Bjorkman, L. (2017). Bisphenol A concentration in human saliva related to dental polymer-based fillings. <i>Clinical oral investigations</i>, 21(8), 2561-2568. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00784-017-2055-9</p>	<p>Norway: Cross sectional with control</p>	<p>Quantify salivary concentrations BPA and assess if dental composite fillings associated with higher BPA levels in saliva</p>	<p>Adult (20-35yrs)</p>
<p>Berge, T. L. L., Lygre, G. B., Lie, S. A., Lindh, C. H., & Björkman, L. (2019). Bisphenol A in human saliva and urine before and after treatment with dental polymer-based restorative materials. <i>EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF ORAL SCIENCES</i>, 127(5), 435-444. https://doi.org/10.1111/eos.12647</p>	<p>Norway: Pre-Post</p>	<p>Quantify salivary/urinary BPA concentrations before and after treatment with dental polymer-based restorative materials to assess if material associated with increased BPA levels</p>	<p>Mix: (16-40yrs)</p>

<p>Björkman, L., Lundekvam Birgitte, F., Lægreid, T., Bertelsen Bjørn, I., Morild, I., Lilleng Peer, K., Lind, B., Palm, B., & Vahter, M. (2007). Mercury in human brain, blood, muscle and toenails in relation to exposure: an autopsy study. <i>Environmental Health</i>, 6(1). https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069x-6-29</p>	<p>Norway: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Elucidate relationships between on the one hand MeHg and I-Hg in human brain and other tissues, including blood, and on the other Hg exposure via dental amalgam in a fish-eating population. In addition, the use of blood and toenails as biological indicator media for inorganic and organic mercury (MeHg) in the tissues was evaluated</p>	<p>Elucidate relationships between on the one hand MeHg and I-Hg in human brain and other tissues, including blood, and on the other Hg exposure via dental amalgam in a fish-eating population. In addition, the use of blood and toenails as biological indicator media for inorganic and organic mercury (MeHg) in the tissues was evaluated</p>
<p>Bloching, M., Reich, W., Schubert, J., Grummt, T., & Sandner, A. (2008). Micronucleus rate of buccal mucosal epithelial cells in relation to oral hygiene and dental factors. <i>Oral oncology</i>, 44(3), 220-226. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.oraloncology.2007.02.002</p>	<p>Germany : Cross sectional</p>	<p>Investigate possible association between cytogenetic damages and dental status. Review extent individual oral hygiene habits, cariologic and periodontal as well as prosthetic status of study participants possess influence on epithelial cells of the buccal mucosa</p>	<p>Adult (30-60yrs)</p>
<p>Bocca 2016 Human biomonitoring of metals in adults living near a waste-to energy incinerator in ante-operam phase: Focus on reference values and health-based assessments</p>	<p>Italy: Cross sectional study with comparison group</p>	<p>1) Establish reference values for several metals in Italian population living near WTE plant at pre-operational period; 2) evaluate differences in exposure across population subsets and identify important predictors of exposure; 3) compare data with other HBM studies; 4) estimate %age of population with exposures exceeding health-based reference levels available for metals; 5) interpret HBM data in a risk-assessment context for individual and combined exposure to</p>	<p>Adults (36-69yrs)</p>

Camacho-Alonso, F., Sánchez-Siles, M., & Águila Osmundo, G. d. (2013). No Evidence of Genotoxic Damage in a Group of Patients with Titanium Dental Implants and Different Metal Restorations in the Oral Cavity. <i>Clinical Implant Dentistry And Related Research</i> , 17(4), 811-821. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/cid.12163	Spain: Cross-sectional with control/Case control	Detect concentration of metal ions in patients with dental implants, to evaluate whether their release might be influenced by presence of other metals, and assay whether these ions might provoke genotoxic damage in oral mucosa cells	Patients: Adults (30-54yrs)
Castano, A., Sanchez-Rodriguez Jinny, E., Canas, A., Esteban, M., Navarro, C., Rodriguez-Garcia Ana, C., Arribas, M., Diaz, G., & Jimenez-Guerrero Jose, A. (2012). Hg, lead and Cd levels in the urine of 170 Spanish adults: a pilot human biomonitoring study. <i>International journal of hygiene and environmental health</i> , 215(2), 191-195. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2011.09.001	Spain: Cross sectional with comparison	Determine reference levels for several biomarkers, especially heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants and cotinine, in urine, whole blood, serum and hair	Adults 23–66yrs
Cesbron, A., Sausseureau, E., Mahieu, L., Couland, I., Guerbet, M., & Goulle, J.-P. (2013). Metallic profile of whole blood and plasma in a series of 106 healthy volunteers. <i>Journal of analytical toxicology</i> , 37(7), 401-405. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jat/bkt046	France: Cross sectional with comparison	Compare and assess any changes in profile of whole blood and plasma in a series of 106 healthy volunteers, particularly due to environment	Hospital staff volunteer (<25->_55)
Chung, S.-Y., Kwon, H., Choi, Y.-H., Karmaus, W., Merchant Anwar, T., Song, K.-B., Sakong, J., Ha, M., Hong, Y.-C., & Kang, D. (2012). Dental composite fillings and bisphenol A among children: a survey in South Korea. <i>International dental journal</i> , 62(2), 65-69. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1875-595X.2011.00089.x	South Korea: Cross sectional	Investigate relationship between urinary BPA concentration and composite restorations and sealants among South Korean children	Children (8-9yrs)
Croes, K., De Coster, S., De Galan, S., Morrens, B., Loots, I., de Mieroop Els, V., Nelen, V., Sioen, I., Bruckers, L., Nawrot Tim, S., Colles, A., Den Hond, E., Schoeters, G., Van Larebeke, N., Baeyens, W., & Gao, Y. (2013). Health effects in the Flemish population in relation to low levels of Hg exposure: From organ to transcriptome level. <i>International Journal Of Hygiene And Environmental Health</i> , 217(2-3), 239-247. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2013.06.004	Finland: Cross-sectional with control/Case control	Main objectives: (1) determine regional Hg-T and MMHg levels in blood and reference level of Hg-T and MMHg in hair for different age classes in Flanders; (2) determine influence of age; (3) compare on sub-population blood and hair levels in same individuals; (4) assess relations between Hg in hair and possible sources e.g. fish consumption and DA; (5) assess dose–effect relations between hair Hg hair and health effect markers including gene expression	Group 1 (FLEHS 1 programme) 3 age groups: Newborns and mothers and adolescents and adults. Group 2 (FLEHS 2 programme) 2 age groups: mothers and newborns and adolescents

<p>Crowe, W., Doherty, L., Watson, G., Armstrong, D., Ball, E., Magee, P., Allsopp, P., Bell, A., Strain, J. J., & McSorley, E. (2016). Hg in Hair Is Inversely Related to Disease Associated Damage in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus. <i>INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND PUBLIC HEALTH</i>, 13(1). https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph13010075</p>	<p>Ireland: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Investigate relationship between Hg exposure and disease activity and disease associated damage</p>	<p>Adults (Mean: 48yrs)</p>
<p>Dack K, Huang P, Taylor CM, Rai D, Lewis SJ. Environmental and genetic predictors of whole blood Hg and selenium concentrations in pregnant women in a UK birth cohort. <i>Environ Adv.</i> 2024 Apr;15:100469. doi: 10.1016/j.envadv.2023.100469</p>	<p>UK: Prospective cohort</p>	<p>Estimate relative importance of predictors of Hg and Se concentrations in blood samples taken from pregnant women</p>	<p>Pregnant women</p>
<p>Di Pietro, A., Visalli, G., La Maestra, S., Micale, R., Baluce, B., Matarese, G., Cingano, L., & Scoglio Maria, E. (2008). Biomonitoring of DNA damage in peripheral blood lymphocytes of subjects with dental restorative fillings. <i>Mutation research</i>, 650(2), 115-122. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.mrgentox.2007.10.023</p>	<p>Italy: Cross sectional with comparison group</p>	<p>Assess genotoxicity of dental restorative compounds in peripheral blood lymphocytes of young exposed subjects vs controls</p>	<p>Adults (18-27yrs)</p>
<p>Diez, S., Montuori, P., Pagano, A., Sarnacchiaro, P., Bayona Josep, M., & Triassi, M. (2008). Hair Hg levels in an urban population from southern Italy: fish consumption as a determinant of exposure. <i>Environment international</i>, 34(2), 162-167. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2007.07.015</p>	<p>Italy: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Determine influence of fish consumption and number/surface/area of DA fillings on THg levels</p>	<p>Adults (35-45yrs)</p>
<p>Ditrichova, D., Kapralova, S., Tichy, M., Ticha, V., Dobesova, J., Justova, E., Eber, M., & Pirek, P. (2007). Oral lichenoid lesions and allergy to dental materials. <i>Biomedical papers of the Medical Faculty of the University Palacky, Olomouc, Czechoslovakia</i>, 151(2), 333-339. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.5507/bp.2007.057</p>	<p>Czech Republic: Cross-sectional with small B&A component (n=6)</p>	<p>Demonstrate contact allergy to dental materials in patients with oral lichenoid lesions using patch tests</p>	<p>Adults (41-74yrs)</p>

<p>Dix-Cooper, L., & Kosatsky, T. (2018). Blood Hg, lead and Cd levels and determinants of exposure among newcomer South and East Asian women of reproductive age living in Vancouver, Canada. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i>, 619/620, 1409-1419. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.11.126</p>	<p>Canada: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Study demographic, health, environmental and cultural determinants of blood levels of Hg, Pb and Cd among newcomer South and East Asian women living in and around Vancouver, Canada</p>	<p>Adults (19-45 yrs)</p>
<p>Dulămea Adriana, O., Boşcaiu, V., & Sava Maria, M. (2015). Disability status and dental pathology in multiple sclerosis patients. <i>Multiple Sclerosis And Related Disorders</i>, 4(6), 567-571. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msard.2015.09.001</p>	<p>Romania: Cross sectional</p>	<p>(1) Achieve better understanding of MS evolution; (2) identify significant associations between dental pathology and clinical course of MS</p>	<p>MS patients: Adults (mean age 39.97yrs)</p>
<p>Duncan, A., O'Reilly, D. S., McDonald, E. B., Watkins, T. R., & Taylor, M. (2011). Thirty-five year review of a Hg monitoring service for Scottish dental practices. <i>Comment in: Br Dent J</i>. 2011 Feb 12;210(3):122-3 PMID: 21311536 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21311536], 210(3), E2. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/sj.bdj.2011.49</p>	<p>Scotland: Retrospective service evaluation/ cohort</p>	<p>Review Hg monitoring service offered to staff in dental practices in Scotland</p>	<p>Dentists+their staff</p>

<p>Dunn Julie, E., Trachtenberg Felicia, L., Barregard, L., Bellinger, D., & McKinlay, S. (2008). Scalp hair and U-Hg content of children in the Northeast United States: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 107(1), 79-88. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2007.08.015</p>	<p>USA: RCT</p>	<p>Describe levels and correlates/predictors of scalp hair and U-Hg in 534 New England Children's Amalgam Trial (NECAT) participants, aged 6–10yrs and without exposure to DA at baseline</p>	<p>Paediatric patients (6-10yrs)</p>
<p>Dutton Daniel, J., Fyie, K., Faris, P., Brunel, L., & Emery Jc, H. (2013). The association between amalgam dental surfaces and U-Hg levels in a sample of Albertans, a prevalence study. <i>Journal of occupational medicine and toxicology</i> (London, England), 8(1), 22. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1745-6673-8-22</p>	<p>Canada: Retrospective observational</p>	<p>Quantify relationship between no. DA surfaces and U- Hg levels</p>	<p>Patients: Adult (Mean age 49.3, SD 11.6)</p>
<p>Echeverria D, Woods JS, Heyer NJ, Martin MD, Rohlman DS, Farin FM, et al. The association between serotonin transporter gene promotor polymorphism (5-HTTLPR) and elemental Hg exposure on mood and behavior in humans. <i>J Toxicol Environ Health A</i> [Internet]. 2010 [cited 2018 Jan 16];73(15):1003-20. Available from: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2882654/pdf/nihms192483.pdf</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Questions if subgroups of humans with 5-HTTLPR polymorphism at greater risk for Hg^o-mediated CNS effects at comparable exposure levels</p>	<p>Adults dental professionals (dentists and dental assistants)</p>
<p>Elli 2015 Increased Hg Levels in Patients with Celiac Disease following a Gluten-Free Regimen. <i>Gastroenterology Research and Practice</i> Volume 2015, Article ID 953042, 6 pages http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2015/953042</p>	<p>Italy: Cross sectional with control</p>	<p>Evaluate blood and urinary Hg in celiac patients</p>	<p>CD patients: Adults (Mean age 40.4 ± 7.5; 40.1 ± 9.7; 39.6 ± 10.9)</p>

<p>Emeny Rebecca, T., Korrick Susan, A., Li, Z., Nadeau, K., Madan, J., Jackson, B., Baker, E., & Karagas Margaret, R. (2019). Prenatal exposure to Hg in relation to infant infections and respiratory symptoms in the New Hampshire Birth Cohort Study. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 171, 523-529. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.01.026</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Investigate association of biomarkers of prenatal Hg exposure and maternal silver-Hg DAs with occurrence of infant allergy, respiratory infection, and respiratory symptoms in first year of life</p>	<p>Maternal exposure</p>
<p>Forysova, K., Pinkr-Grafnetterova, A., Maly, M., Krskova, A., Mraz, J., Kasparova, L., Cejchanova, M., Sochorova, L., Rodlova, S., & Cerna, M. (2017). Urinary Cd and Cotinine Levels and Hair Hg Levels in Czech Children and Their Mothers Within the Framework of the COPHES/DEMOCOPHES Projects. <i>Archives of environmental contamination and toxicology</i>, 73(3), 421-430. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00244-017-0412-y</p>	<p>17 European countries: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Publish results obtained in Czech Republic within DEMOCOPHES project separately as comparison with already existing Czech data concerning urinary Cd and Hg in hair</p>	<p>Children (6-11yrs) and mothers of reproductive age</p>

<p>France, S., Alenka, Falnoga, I., Briski Alenka, S., Zavbi, M., Osredkar, J., Skitek, M., & Marc, J. (2024). Reference intervals of 24 trace elements in blood, plasma and erythrocytes for the Slovenian adult population. Erratum in: Clin Chem Lab Med. 2024 Aug 26;62(11):2335. doi: 10.1515/cclm-2024-0868 PMID: 39192623 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/39192623], 62(5), 946-957. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1515/cclm-2023-0731</p>	<p>Slovenia: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Establish population- and laboratory-specific reference intervals for Slovenian adult population for 24 trace elements in blood, plasma and erythrocytes and evaluate impact of gender, age, seafood consumption, smoking habits and amalgam fillings on level of trace elements</p>	<p>Adults: 18-65yrs</p>
<p>Geer Laura, A., Persad Malini, D., Palmer Christopher, D., Steuerwald Amy, J., Dalloul, M., Abulafia, O., & Parsons Patrick, J. (2012). Assessment of prenatal Hg exposure in a predominately Caribbean immigrant community in Brooklyn, NY. Journal of Environmental Monitoring, 14(3), 1035-1043. https://doi.org/10.1039/c2em10835f</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>1) Assess total Hg levels in both urine specimens from pregnant women, and cord blood; and 2) examine environmental sources of exposure from convenience sample in a predominantly Caribbean immigrant population in Brooklyn, New York</p>	<p>Patients: Pregnant women (18-45yrs)</p>
<p>Geier David, A., & Geier Mark, R. (2021). DAs and the Incidence Rate of Arthritis among American Adults. Clinical medicine insights. Arthritis and musculoskeletal disorders, 14, 11795441211016261. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/11795441211016261</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional with comparison group</p>	<p>Evaluate relationship between Hg (Hg)-based DAs and arthritis diagnoses among US adults</p>	<p>Adults (20-80yrs)</p>

<p>Geier David, A., & Geier Mark, R. (2021). Reported asthma and DA exposure among adults in the United States: An assessment of the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. <i>SAGE open medicine</i>, 9, 20503121211048677. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/20503121211048677</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Evaluate relationship between DA exposure and risk of reported asthma diagnoses</p>	<p>Adults (20-80yrs)</p>
<p>Geier David, A., & Geier Mark, R. (2024). Estimated Hg vapor exposure from amalgams among American pregnant women. <i>Human & experimental toxicology</i>, 43, 9603271241231945. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/09603271241231945</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional with comparison group</p>	<p>Examine impact of Hg (Hg) vapor exposure from amalgams among all American pregnant women</p>	<p>Patient: Pregnant women (22-44yrs)</p>
<p>Geier David, A., Kern Janet, K., & Geier Mark, R. (2009). A prospective study of prenatal mercury exposure from maternal dental amalgams and autism severity. <i>Acta neurobiologiae experimentalis</i>, 69(2), 189-197. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.55782/ane-2009-1744</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Examine increased Hg exposure from maternal dental amalgams during pregnancy among 100 qualifying participants born between 1990–1999 and diagnosed with DSM-IV autism (severe) or ASD (mild)</p>	<p>Maternal exposure: Child (min. 6yrs)</p>
<p>Geier, D. A., & Geier, M. R. (2022). DA fillings and Hg vapor safety limits in American adults. <i>Human & experimental toxicology</i>, 41, 9603271221106341. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/09603271221106341</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Examine impact of Hg vapor exposure from amalgams in American adults</p>	<p>Patients: Adults (21-66yrs)</p>

<p>Geier, D. A., Carmody, T., Kern, J. K., King, P. G., & Geier Mark, R. (2012). A dose-dependent relationship between Hg exposure from DAs and U-Hg levels: a further assessment of the Casa Pia Children's DA Trial. <i>Human & experimental toxicology</i>, 31(1), 11-17. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0960327111417264</p>	<p>USA: RCT</p>	<p>Determine whether there was a significant dose-dependent correlation between increasing Hg exposure from DAs and U-Hg levels</p>	<p>Patients: children (8-12yrs)</p>
<p>Gerhardsson, L., & Lundh, T. (2010). Metal concentrations in blood and hair in pregnant females in southern Sweden. <i>Journal of environmental health</i>, 72(6), 37-41. http://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&PAGE=reference&D=med8&NEWS=N&AN=20104833</p>	<p>Sweden: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Determine concentrations of Hg, Pb, and Cd in whole blood and Hg in hair in pregnant females in an inland and a coastline city in southern Sweden. Evaluate possible regional differences in Sweden</p>	<p>Pregnant women</p>
<p>Ghezal-Ahmadi, D., Engel, A., Weidemann, J., Budnik Lygia, T., Baur, X., Frick, U., Hauser, S., & Dahmen, N. (2009). Heavy metal exposure in patients suffering from electromagnetic hypersensitivity. <i>The Science Of The Total Environment</i>, 408(4), 774-778. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2009.11.023</p>	<p>Germany: Case control (matched control group)</p>	<p>Test link between electromagenetic hypersensitivity and heavy metal exposure</p>	<p>Patients: Adults with EM hypersensitivity</p>
<p>Golding, J., Rai, D., Gregory, S., Ellis, G., Emond, A., Iles-Caven, Y., Hibbeln, J., & Taylor, C. (2018). Prenatal Hg exposure and features of autism: a prospective population study. <i>Molecular autism</i>, 9, 30. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13229-018-0215-7</p>	<p>UK: Longitudinal</p>	<p>Test whether prenatal exposure from total blood Hg in first half of pregnancy is associated with autism risk or of extreme levels of autistic traits</p>	<p>Maternal exposure</p>

<p>Golding, J., Steer Colin, D., Gregory, S., Lowery, T., Hibbeln Joseph, R., & Taylor Caroline, M. (2016). Dental associations with blood Hg in pregnant women. Comment in: J Evid Based Dent Pract. 2017 Jun;17(2):139-141 PMID: 28501064 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28501064], 44(3), 216-222. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/cdoe.12208</p>	<p>UK: Cross sectional (part of same longitudinal study as Golding 2018)</p>	<p>Determine extent to which DA contributes to TBHg levels of pregnant women in the UK</p>	<p>Pregnant women</p>
<p>Goodrich Jaclyn, M., Basu, N., Franzblau, A., & Dolinoy Dana, C. (2013). Hg biomarkers and DNA methylation among Michigan dental professionals. Environmental and molecular mutagenesis, 54(3), 195-203. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/em.21763</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional</p>	<p>. Hypothesize methylHg and inorganic Hg exposures from fish consumption and DA, respectively, may be associated with altered DNA methylation at global repetitive elements (long interspersed elements, LINE-1) and candidate genes related to epigenetic processes (DNMT1) and protection against Hg toxicity (SEPW1, SEPP1)</p>	<p>HCP: dentists, dental hygienists, dental assistants</p>
<p>Goodrich Jaclyn, M., Chou, H.-N., Gruninger Stephen, E., Franzblau, A., & Basu, N. (2016). Exposures of dental professionals to elemental Hg and methylHg. Journal of exposure science & environmental epidemiology, 26(1), 78-85. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/jes.2015.52</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Determine sources of exposure to methylHg and elemental Hg among dental professionals and to measure Hg biomarker levels</p>	<p>HCP: dentists, dental hygienists, dental assistants, dental students, office managers</p>
<p>Goodrich Jaclyn, M., Wang, Y., Gillespie Brenda, W., Werner Robert, A., Franzblau, A., & Basu, N. (2012). MethylHg and elemental Hg differentially associate with blood pressure among dental professionals. International Journal Of Hygiene And Environmental Health, 216(2), 195-201. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2012.03.001</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Increase understanding of association between Hg exposure (methylHg and elemental Hg) and blood pressure measures in dental professional cohort exposed to both Hg forms</p>	<p>Dental professionals (NR)</p>
<p>Goodrich Jaclyn, M., Wang, Y., Gillespie, B., Werner, R., Franzblau, A., & Basu, N. (2011). Glutathione enzyme and selenoprotein polymorphisms associate with Hg biomarker levels in Michigan dental professionals. Toxicology & Applied Pharmacology, 257(2), 301-308. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2011.09.014</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Hypothesize polymorphisms in key glutathione synthesizing enzyme, glutathione s-transferase, and selenoprotein genes underlie inter-individual differences in Hg body burden as assessed by analytical Hg measurement in urine and hair, biomarkers of elemental Hg and methylHg</p>	<p>HCP: dentists, dental hygienists, dental assistants, dental students, office managers</p>

<p>Grzunov, L., Judita, Matek, S., Marijana, Piasek, M., Jurasovic, J., Varnai Veda, M., Sulimanec, G., Antonija, & Orct, T. (2016). Use of human milk in the assessment of toxic metal exposure and essential element status in breastfeeding women and their infants in coastal Croatia. <i>Journal of trace elements in medicine and biology : organ of the Society for Minerals and Trace Elements (GMS)</i>, 38, 117-125. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2016.08.002</p>	<p>Croatia: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Assess health risks in breastfeeding women in coastal area of Republic of Croatia and their infants (N=107) due to maternal exposure to Cd and Pb via cigarette smoking, and Hg via seafood and DA fillings, and interaction with essential elements</p>	<p>Maternal exposure: postpartum women (mean 30yrs)</p>
<p>Gundacker, C., Fröhlich, S., Graf-Rohrmeister, K., Eibenberger, B., Jessenig, V., Gicic, D., Prinz, S., Wittmann Karl, J., Zeisler, H., Vallant, B., Pollak, A., & Husslein, P. (2010). Perinatal lead and Hg exposure in Austria. <i>The Science Of The Total Environment</i>, 408(23), 5744-5749. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2010.07.079</p>	<p>Austria: Prospective cohort</p>	<p>Compare perinatal Pb and Hg concentrations and explore potential association between Pb and Hg exposure and newborn anthropometry</p>	<p>Maternal exposure: pregnant women-child pairs</p>
<p>Guzzi, G., Fogazzi Giovanni, B., Cantu, M., Minoia, C., Ronchi, A., Pigatto Paolo, D., & Severi, G. (2008). DA, Hg toxicity, and renal autoimmunity. <i>Journal of environmental pathology, toxicology and oncology : official organ of the International Society for Environmental Toxicology and Cancer</i>, 27(2), 147-155. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1615/jenvironpatholtoxiconcol.v27.i2.70</p>	<p>Australia: Cross sectional (retrospective review of records to identify participants)</p>	<p>Test occurrence of specific antibodies to antiglomerular basement membrane (anti-GBM-IgG) among individuals with adverse effects to Hg from DA fillings</p>	<p>Adults (18-75yrs). HCP Dentists/Dental assistants (n=3)</p>

<p>Halbach, S., Vogt, S., Kohler, W., Felgenhauer, N., Welzl, G., Kremers, L., Zilker, T., & Melchart, D. (2008). Blood and U-Hg levels in adult amalgam patients of a randomized controlled trial: interaction of Hg species in erythrocytes. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 107(1), 69-78. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2007.07.005</p>	<p>Germany: RCT</p>	<p>1) Investigate internal exposure to amalgam-related Hg from kinetics of inorganic Hg in plasma and erythrocytes after amalgam removal, 2) estimate amalgam-related absorbed dose</p>	<p>Patients: Adults (20-50yrs)</p>
<p>Hertz-Picciotto, I., Green, P. G., Delwiche, L., Hansen, R., Walker, C., & Pessah, I. N. (2010). Blood Hg concentrations in CHARGE Study children with and without autism. <i>Environmental Health Perspectives</i>, 118(1), 161-166. https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.0900736</p>	<p>USA: Retrospective observational -Case control</p>	<p>Compare blood total Hg concentrations in children with autism or ASD and typically developing controls in population-based samples, and determined role of fish consumption</p>	<p>Children (20-60mnths)</p>
<p>Heyer Nicholas, J., Echeverria, D., Farin Federico, M., & Woods James, S. (2008). The association between serotonin transporter gene promoter polymorphism (5-HTTLPR), self-reported symptoms, and dental Hg exposure. <i>Journal of toxicology and environmental health. Part A</i>, 71(19), 1318-1326. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15287390802240850</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Examine effects of 5-HTTLPR polymorphism on self-reported neurobehavioral consequences of low-level occupational Hg₀ exposure in dental professional population</p>	<p>HCP: Dentists, dental assistants</p>
<p>Heyer Nicholas, J., Echeverria, D., Martin Michael, D., Farin Federico, M., & Woods James, S. (2009). Catechol O-methyltransferase (COMT) VAL158MET functional polymorphism, dental Hg exposure, and self-reported symptoms and mood. <i>Journal of toxicology and environmental health. Part A</i>, 72(9), 599-609. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15287390802706405</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>The independent and combined effects of Hg₀ exposure and the COMT Val158Met polymorphism were evaluated in dental professionals with prolonged occupational Hg₀ exposure</p>	<p>HCP: Dentists, dental assistants</p>

<p>Hruba, F., Cerna, M., Chen, C., Harari, F., Horvat, M., Koppova, K., Krskova, A., Laamech, J., Li, Y.-F., Lofmark, L., Lundh, T., Lyoussi, B., Mazej, D., Osredkar, J., Pawlas, K., Pawlas, N., Prokopowicz, A., Rentschler, G., Snoj, T., Janja, Sommar, J., Spevackova, V., Spiric, Z., Skerfving, S., & Bergdahl Ingvar, A. (2023). A regional comparison of children's blood Cd, lead, and Hg in rural, urban and industrial areas of six European countries, and China, Ecuador, and Morocco. <i>International journal of occupational medicine and environmental health</i>, 36(3), 349-364. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.13075/ijomeh.1896.02139</p>	<p>Six european contries, china, ecuador and morroco: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Evaluate if blood Cd, Pb and Hg in children differ regionally in 9 countries, and identify factors correlating with exposure</p>	<p>Children (7-11yrs)</p>
<p>Hruba, F., Stromberg, U., Cerna, M., Chen, C., Harari, F., Harari, R., Horvat, M., Koppova, K., Kos, A., Krskova, A., Krsnik, M., Laamech, J., Li, Y.-F., Lofmark, L., Lundh, T., Lundstrom, N.-G., Lyoussi, B., Mazej, D., Osredkar, J., Pawlas, K., Pawlas, N., Prokopowicz, A., Rentschler, G., Spevackova, V., Spiric, Z., Tratnik, J., Skerfving, S., & Bergdahl Ingvar, A. (2012). Blood Cd, Hg, and lead in children: an international comparison of cities in six European countries, and China, Ecuador, and Morocco. <i>Environment international</i>, 41, 29-34. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2011.12.001</p>	<p>Six european contries, china, ecuador and morroco: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Describe/compare blood Cd, Pb and Hg in children in six European, and three non-European cities, and identify determinants of these exposures</p>	<p>Children (7-14yrs)</p>
<p>Jaakkola Maritta, S., Leino, T., Tammilehto, L., Ylöstalo, P., Kuosma, E., & Alanko, K. (2007). Respiratory effects of exposure to methacrylates among dental assistants. <i>Allergy</i>, 62(6), 648-654. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1398-9995.2007.01379.x</p>	<p>Finland: Cross sectional with comparison group</p>	<p>Investigate relation methacrylates exposure to occurrenceof respiratory symptoms and diseases among dental assistants</p>	<p>Female dental assistants</p>
<p>Jarosinska, D., Horvat, M., Sallsten, G., Mazzolai, B., Dabkowska, B., Prokopowicz, A., Biesiada, M., & Barregard, L. (2008). U-Hg and biomarkers of early renal dysfunction in environmentally and occupationally exposed adults: a three-country study. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 108(2), 224-232. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2008.06.005</p>	<p>Sweden, Italy and Poland: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Assess environmental and occupational exposure to Hg from CA plants and potential association with biomarkers of early renal dysfunction</p>	<p>Adults (18-65yrs)</p>
<p>Kim Dae, S., Kim Geun, B., Kang, T.-S., & Ahn, S. (2011). Total and methyl Hg in maternal and cord blood of pregnant women in Korea. <i>Toxicology And Environmental Health Sciences</i>, 3(4), 254-257. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s13530-011-0099-9</p>	<p>South Korea: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Investigate Hg concentrations among pregnant women and main causes of Hg exposure in Korea</p>	<p>Maternal exposure-pregnant women</p>

<p>Kim, D. S., Kim, J. H., Yang, W. H., Moon, J. S., & Son, B. S. (2010). Biomonitoring of U-Hg in Korean school children. <i>MOLECULAR & CELLULAR TOXICOLOGY</i>, 6(4), 353-360. https://doi.org/10.1007/s13273-010-0047-9</p>	<p>Korea: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Assess Hg exposure in schoolchildren 7-13yrs of age (n=274) using U-Hg analysis</p>	<p>Children: 7-13yrs</p>
<p>Kim, T. W., Kim, W. I., Mun, J. H., Song, M., Kim, H. S., Kim, B. S., ... & Ko, H. C. (2015). Patch testing with dental screening series in oral disease. <i>Annals of dermatology</i>, 27(4), 389-393.</p>	<p>Korea: Retrospective database review</p>	<p>Analyze positive patch test results in oral disease patients and evaluate clinical relevance of oral diseases with contact allergy to dental materials</p>	<p>Adults (20-71yrs)</p>
<p>Kindler, S., Seebauer, C., Mksoud, M., Samietz, S., Kocher, T., Holtfreter, B., Lucas, C., Volzke, H., Metelmann, H.-R., Rau, A., & Ittermann, T. (2023). Impact of dental restorations and removable prostheses on potentially malignant oral mucosal disorders in the general population. <i>The Journal of prosthetic dentistry</i>, 129(1), 89-95. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.prosdent.2022.05.017</p>	<p>Germany: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Determine relationship between presence of amalgam and CRR, crowns and fixed partial dentures, and removable prostheses in potentially malignant disorders</p>	<p>Adults</p>
<p>Kingman, A., Hyman, J., Masten Scott, A., Jayaram, B., Smith, C., Eichmiller, F., Arnold Michael, C., Wong Paul, A., Schaeffer James, M., Solanki, S., & Dunn William, J. (2012). Bisphenol A and other compounds in human saliva and urine associated with the placement of composite restorations. <i>Comment in: J Evid Based Dent Pract</i>. 2013 Jun;13(2):64-6 PMID: 23773471 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23773471], 143(12), 1292-1302. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.14219/jada.archive.2012.0090</p>	<p>USA: Before and After</p>	<p>Assess BPA salivary and urinary concentrations and other compounds before/after placement of resin-based composite dental restoration</p>	<p>Patients</p>
<p>Knezović, Z., Trgo, M., & Sutlović, D. (2016). Monitoring Hg environment pollution through bioaccumulation in meconium. <i>Process Safety & Environmental Protection: Transactions of the Institution of Chemical Engineers Part B</i>, 101, 2-8. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2016.01.013</p>	<p>Croatia: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Determine Hg bioaccumulation in humans from different environmental sources, through non-invasive biomaterial sampling. Identify environmental impact on Hg level in human body</p>	<p>Mother-newborn pairs</p>

<p>Kobal Alfred, B., Snoj, T., Janja, Mazej, D., Fajon, V., Gibicar, D., Miklavcic, A., Kocman, D., Kotnik, J., Sesek, B., Alenka, Osredkar, J., Krsnik, M., Prezelj, M., Knap, C., Krizaj, B., Liang, L., & Horvat, M. (2017). Exposure to Hg in susceptible population groups living in the former Hg mining town of Idrija, Slovenia. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 152, 434-445. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2016.06.037</p>	<p>Slovenia: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Evaluate environmental distribution and concentrations of Hg in surrounds of Idrija, and estimate exposure of school-age children and pregnant women to Hg^o, methyl Hg and inorganic Hg through inhalation of ambient air, ingestion of drinking water and locally grown seasonal vegetables, + intake of methyl Hg from fish consumption. Possible interactions of Hg with selenium (Se) and antioxidative enzymes examined in subgroup</p>	<p>First study: Pregnant women Second study: Children: 6-11yrs</p>
<p>Kristoffersen Agnete, E., Alræk, T., Stub, T., Hamre Harald, J., Björkman, L., & Musial, F. (2016). Health Complaints Attributed to DA: A Retrospective Survey Exploring Perceived Health Changes Related to Amalgam Removal. <i>The Open Dentistry Journal</i>, 10(1), 739-751. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2174/1874210601610010739</p>	<p>Norway: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Assess total symptom load in patients with all amalgam fillings removed, and investigate self-reported improvement of health relating to precautions taken under amalgam removal and time since removal</p>	<p>Patients: ll amalgam fillings removed</p>
<p>Kruzikova, K., Kensova, R., Blahova, J., Harustiakova, D., & Svobodova, Z. (2009). Using human hair as an indicator for exposure to Hg. <i>Neuro endocrinology letters</i>, 30 Suppl 1, 177-181. http://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&PAGE=reference&D=med7&NEWS=N&AN=20027167</p>	<p>Czech Republic: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Assess Hg exposure in Czech Republic by performing Hg determination using human hair</p>	<p>Population 2-66yrs old</p>
<p>Kruzikova, K., Modra, H., Kensova, R., Skocovska, B., Wlasow, T., Svoboda, T., & Svobodova, Z. (2008). Hg in human hair as an indicator of the fish consumption. <i>Neuro endocrinology letters</i>, 29(5), 675-679. http://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&PAGE=reference&D=med7&NEWS=N&AN=18987591</p>	<p>Czech Republic: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Compare hair-Hg content in children with various quantity fish consumption (increased or reduced)</p>	<p>Children (9-17yrs)</p>
<p>Lee, J.-H., Yi, S.-K., Kim, S.-Y., Kim, J.-S., Son, S.-A., Jeong, S.-H., & Kim, J.-B. (2017). Salivary bisphenol A levels and their association with composite resin restoration. <i>Chemosphere</i>, 172, 46-51. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.12.123</p>	<p>Republic of Korea: Before and After</p>	<p>Measure changes in salivary BPA level related with CRR</p>	<p>Patients: Age not clearly specified. 13 < 40yrs, 17 40yrs old or more</p>

<p>Letinic, J. G., Saric, M. M., Piasek, M., Jurasovic, J., Varnai, V. M., Grgec, A. S., & Orct, T. (2016). Use of human milk in the assessment of toxic metal exposure and essential element status in breastfeeding women and their infants in coastal Croatia. <i>Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology</i>, 38, 117-125. http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0946672X16301948</p>	<p>Croatia: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Assess health risks in breastfeeding women in coastal area of Republic of Croatia and their infants (N=107) due to maternal exposure to Cd and Pb via cigarette smoking, and Hg via seafood and DA fillings, and interaction with essential elements</p>	<p>Maternal exposure: Postpartum women (Mean age 30, SD 5)</p>
<p>Link, B., Gabrio, T., Piechotowski, I., Zollner, I., & Schwenk, M. (2007). Baden-Wuerttemberg Environmental Health Survey (BW-EHS) from 1996 to 2003: toxic metals in blood and urine of children. <i>International journal of hygiene and environmental health</i>, 210(3-4), 357-371. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2007.01.031</p>	<p>Germany: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Report body burden of toxic elements As, Hg, lead, and Cd in children</p>	<p>Children: 4th graders</p>

<p>Link, B., Gabrio, T., Zollner, I., Jaroni, H., Piechotowski, I., Schilling, B., Felder-Kennel, A., Flicker-Klein, A., Konig, M., Maisner, V., Schick, K. H., & Fischer, G. (2012). Decrease of internal exposure to chlororganic compounds and heavy metals in children in Baden-Wurtemberg between 1996/1997 and 2008/2009. <i>International journal of hygiene and environmental health</i>, 215(2), 196-201. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2011.10.017</p>	<p>Germany: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Concentrations of DDE,HCB, PCBs and PCDD/PCDF in blood and urine monitored in 9- to 11-year-old children every second year starting in 1996. For the organochlorinated compounds (Link et al., 2005; Gabrio et al., 2005) and heavy metals (Wilhelm et al., 2006; Link et al., 2007b) results have already been published. The results of two additional investigation periods (2004/2005 and 2008/2009) presented</p>	<p>Children (9-11yrs)</p>
<p>Lomaga, M., Polak, S., Grushka, M., & Walsh Scott, R. (2009). Results of Patch Testing in Patients Diagnosed with Oral Lichen Planus. <i>Journal Of Cutaneous Medicine And Surgery</i>, 13(2), 88-95. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2310/7750.2008.08017</p>	<p>Canada: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Elucidate association of contact allergy and OLL, reviewed patch-test readings in patients diagnosed with OLP-like lesions</p>	<p>Adults (19-76)</p>
<p>Lopez-Jornet, P., & Camacho-Alonso, F. (2008). Do metal restorations in mouth alter clinical and histological appearance of oral lichen planus? <i>The New York state dental journal</i>, 74(6), 40-43. http://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&PAGE=reference&D=med7&NEWS=N&N=19195238</p>	<p>Spain: Cross sectional with comparison</p>	<p>Determine whether clinical and histopathological differences exist between patients with oral lichen planus (OLP) with DA and those without</p>	<p>Adults</p>
<p>Lyapina, M. G., Dencheva, M. S., Krasteva, A. Z., Nikolov, G. S., Cekova, M. P., Deliverska, M. S., & Yaneva, A. I. K. (2016). BIOMONITORING OF URINARY LEVELS OF BISPHENOL A. <i>COMPTES RENDUS DE L ACADEMIE BULGARE DES SCIENCES</i>, 69(6), 807-814.</p>	<p>Bulgaria: Cross sectional with a control group</p>	<p>Evaluate urinary BPA levels , choosing as target groups one of students of dental medicine, and representatives of general population – dental patients, treated with dental materials containing BPA derivatives</p>	<p>Students of dental medicine, patients without occupational exposure to materials being source of BPA</p>
<p>Lyapina, M. G., Dencheva, M., Krasteva-Panova, A., Tzekova-Yaneva, M., Deliverska, M., & Kisselova-Yaneva, A. (2016). CONCOMITANT SENSITIZATION TO GLUTARALDEHYDE AND METHACRYLIC MONOMERS AMONG DENTISTS AND THEIR PATIENTS. <i>MEDYCYNA PRACTY</i>, 67(3), 311-320. https://doi.org/10.13075/mp.5893.00106</p>	<p>Bulgaria: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Evaluate frequency and risk of concomitant sensitization to some methacrylic monomers (MMA, TEGDMA, EGDMA, Bis-GMA, 2-HEMA and THFMA) and glutaraldehyde in students of dentistry, students from the dental technician school, dental professionals and dental patients</p>	<p>HCP and Patients occupationally exposed dental professionals, students of 3rd, 4th and 6th year of dental medicine, and occupationally unexposed dental patients</p>

<p>Lyapina, M., Dencheva, M., Krasteva, A., Tzekova, M., & Kisselova-Yaneva, A. (2014). Concomitant contact allergy to formaldehyde and methacrylic monomers in students of dental medicine and dental patients. <i>International journal of occupational medicine and environmental health</i>, 27(5), 797-807. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.2478/s13382-014-0314-4</p>	<p>Bulgaria: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Evaluate incidence and risk of cross-sensitization to some methacrylic monomers (MMA, TEGDMA, EGDMA, Bis-GMA, 2-HEMA, and tetrahydrofurfuryl methacry late) and formaldehyde in students of dentistry, dental professionals and dental patients</p>	<p>HCP and Patients: Occupationally exposed dental professionals, students of the 3rd, 4th and 6th year of dental medicine, and occupationally unexposed dental patients</p>
<p>Lye, E., Legrand, M., Clarke, J., & Probert, A. Blood total Hg concentrations in the Canadian population: Canadian Health Measures Survey cycle 1, 2007-2009. <i>Canadian Journal of Public Health</i>, 104(3), e246-251. https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=cul&AN=104189619&site=ehost-live</p>	<p>Canada: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Present total Hg (THg) in blood of Canadians 6-79yrs from first to-date nationally-representative survey</p>	<p>Population: 6-79yrs</p>
<p>Lynde Carrie, B., Grushka, M., & Walsh Scott, R. (2014). Burning Mouth Syndrome. <i>Journal Of Cutaneous Medicine And Surgery</i>, 18(3), 174-179. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2310/7750.2013.13096</p>	<p>Canada: Retrospective cohort study</p>	<p>Determine if delayed-type hypersensitivity reaction may be component in pathogenesis of BMS</p>	<p>Adults with BMS (29-88)</p>
<p>MacAulay, M., Tam, L. E., Santerre, J. P., & Finer, Y. (2017). In Vivo Biodegradation of bisGMA and Urethane-Modified bisGMA-Based Resin Composite Materials. <i>JDR clinical and translational research</i>, 2(4), 397-405. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/2380084417722117</p>	<p>Canada: Before and After</p>	<p>Compare levels of in vivo chemical degradation sustained by bisGMA-based and urethane-modified bisGMAbased resin composit</p>	<p>Patients: Adults</p>

<p>Maserejian Nancy, N., Trachtenberg Felicia, L., Assmann Susan, F., & Barregard, L. (2008). Dental amalgam exposure and urinary mercury levels in children: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. <i>Environmental Health Perspectives</i>, 116(2), 256-262. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1289/ehp.10440</p>	<p>USA: RCT</p>	<p>Determine the most efficient measure of dental amalgam exposure for use in analyses concerning U-Hg in children</p>	<p>Children (6-10yrs)</p>
<p>Maserejian Nancy, N., Trachtenberg Felicia, L., Wheaton Olivia, B., Calafat Antonia, M., Ranganathan, G., Kim, H.-Y., & Hauser, R. (2016). Changes in urinary bisphenol A concentrations associated with placement of dental composite restorations in children and adolescents. <i>Journal of the American Dental Association</i> (1939), 147(8), 620-630. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.adaj.2016.02.019</p>	<p>USA: Before and After</p>	<p>Explore potential association between urinary Bisphenol A Concentrations and CR</p>	<p>Patient: Children (3-17yrs)</p>

<p>McKelvey, W., Alex, B., Chernov, C., Hore, P., Palmer, C. D., Steuerwald, A. J., Parsons, P. J., & Perlman, S. E. (2018). Tracking Declines in Hg Exposure in the New York City Adult Population, 2004-2014. <i>JOURNAL OF URBAN HEALTH-BULLETIN OF THE NEW YORK ACADEMY OF MEDICINE</i>, 95(6), 813-825. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-018-0269-z</p>	<p>USA: Repeated cross sectional study with secondary data analysis</p>	<p>Track impacts of initiatives to reduce exposures over past 10yrs by comparing changes in NYC with changes measured nationally by NHANES. To better understand how major identified sources of Hg exposure in general NYC population (fish consumption, skin-lightening creams, and DAs) explain variation in blood and urine concentrations across sociodemographic subgroups</p>	<p>Adults 20yrs or above</p>
<p>McKinney, C. M., Leroux, B. G., Seminario, A. L., Kim, A., Liu, Z., Samy, S., & Sathyanarayana, S. (2020). A Prospective Cohort Study of Bisphenol A Exposure from Dental Treatment. <i>Journal of dental research</i>, 99(11), 1262-1269. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0022034520934725</p>	<p>USA: Prospective before and after</p>	<p>Quantify extent children are exposed to BPA from dental treatment with bisGMA materials, by amount of treatment and sedation type</p>	<p>Children 4-12yrs</p>
<p>McKinney, C., Rue, T., Sathyanarayana, S., Martin, M., Seminario Ana, L., & DeRouen, T. (2014). Dental sealants and restorations and urinary bisphenol A concentrations in children in the 2003-2004 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. <i>Comment in: J Evid Based Dent Pract</i>. 2014 Dec;14(4):200-2 PMID: 25488874 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/25488874], 145(7), 745-750. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.14219/jada.2014.34</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Hypothesized greater no. dental sealants or restorations would be associated with higher urinary BPA concentrations.</p>	<p>Children 6-19yrs</p>

<p>Melchart, D., Kohler, W., Linde, K., Zilker, T., Kremers, L., Saller, R., & Halbach, S. (2008). Biomonitoring of mercury in patients with complaints attributed to dental amalgam, healthy amalgam bearers, and amalgam-free subjects: a diagnostic study. <i>Clinical toxicology (Philadelphia, Pa.)</i>, 46(2), 133-140. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15563650701324211</p>	<p>Germany: RCT</p>	<p>Investigate the suitability of measurements of mercury (Hg) concentration as a means of identifying patients with health complaints attributed to dental amalgam</p>	<p>Investigate the suitability of measurements of mercury (Hg) concentration as a means of identifying patients with health complaints attributed to dental amalgam</p>
<p>Michalak (2012) Exposure to Ni by hair mineral analysis</p>	<p>Poland: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Investigate exposure to Ni from various sources by investigation of mineral composition of human scalp hair</p>	<p>Healthy volunteers (n=265), mean age 22yrs SD 2</p>
<p>Michalak, I., Chojnacka, K., Saeid, A., & Mikulewicz, M. (2014). Research on Hg levels in scalp hair. <i>Polish Journal of Environmental Studies</i>, 23(3), 793-800. http://www.pjoes.com</p>	<p>Poland: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Evaluate the Hg content in hair of inhabitants of Wroctaw, in southwestern Poland</p>	<p>Population: Adults (average 25yrs (SD10))</p>
<p>Michalak, I., Wołowiec, P., & Chojnacka, K. (2014). Determination of exposure to lead of subjects from southwestern Poland by human hair analysis. <i>Environmental Monitoring & Assessment</i>, 186(4), 2259-2267. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-013-3534-3</p>	<p>Poland: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Investigate exposure to lead from various sources by investigation of mineral composition of human scalp hair</p>	<p>Population: Adults (average 22 yrs (SD2))</p>

<p>Michelsen Vibeke, B., Kopperud Hilde, B. M., Lygre Gunvor, B., Bjorkman, L., Jensen, E., Kleven Inger, S., Svahn, J., & Lygre, H. (2012). Detection and quantification of monomers in unstimulated whole saliva after treatment with resin-based composite fillings in vivo. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF ORAL SCIENCES, 120(1), 89-95. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0722.2011.00897.x</p>	<p>Norway: Before and After</p>	<p>Quantify methacrylate monomers in saliva after treatment with resin-based composite filling material</p>	<p>Patient: Adults (Mean age 54.4 (4.1yrs))</p>
<p>Mittermüller, P., Hiller, K. A., Schmalz, G., & Buchalla, W. (2018). Five hundred patients reporting on adverse effects from dental materials: Frequencies, complaints, symptoms, allergies. DENTAL MATERIALS, 34(12), 1756-1768. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dental.2018.09.011</p>	<p>Germany: Retrospective cross-sectional</p>	<p>Investigate patients reporting on complaints and symptoms to dental materials over a 16-year period</p>	<p>Ct? Patients:</p>
<p>Moen, B., Hollund, B., & Riise, T. (2008). Neurological symptoms among dental assistants: a cross-sectional study. Journal of occupational medicine and toxicology (London, England), 3, 10. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1745-6673-3-10</p>	<p>Norway: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Compare occurrence of neurological symptoms among dental assistants exposed to Hg from work with dental filling material vs similar health personnel with no such exposure</p>	<p>HCP: Dental assistants, Assistant nurses as reference group</p>
<p>Mori, T., Sato, K., Kusaka, Y., Ido, T., Kumagiri, M., Ogasawara, T., & Sano, K. (2007). Positive patch test for Hg possibly from exposure to amalgam. Environmental health and preventive medicine, 12(4), 172-177. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF02897987</p>	<p>Japan: Cross sectional with control</p>	<p>Investigate relationship between positive patch test for Hg and sources of Hg exposure, indicated by concentrations in biological samples from healthy medical students.</p>	<p>Population: Adults</p>

<p>Movassagh, H., Halchenko, Y., Sampath, V., Nygaard Unni, C., Jackson, B., Robbins, D., Li, Z., Nadeau Kari, C., & Karagas Margaret, R. (2021). Maternal gestational Hg exposure in relation to cord blood T cell alterations and placental gene expression signatures. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 201, N.PAG-N.PAG. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111385</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Investigate associations between gestational Hg exposure and frequency of cord blood T cells+placental gene expression</p>	<p>Maternal exposure: Pregnant women (18-45yrs)</p>
<p>Murariu, A., Savin, C., Feier, R., & Balan, A. (2016). Study Regarding the Toxic Effects of Resin-based Dental Materials. <i>REVISTA DE CHIMIE</i>, 67(9), 1876-1878.</p>	<p>Romania: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Highlight toxic effects following dental treatments with materials containing acrylic products e.g. composite resins for crown restoration and acrylic materials entering structure of conventional dental prostheses</p>	<p>HCP: Dentists re: patients</p>
<p>Muris, J., Goossens, A., Gonçalo, M., Bircher Andreas, J., Giménez, A., Foti, C., Rustemeyer, T., Feilzer Albert, J., & Kleverlaan Cornelis, J. (2015). Sensitization to palladium and Ni in Europe and the relationship with oral disease and dental alloys. <i>Contact Dermatitis</i>, 72(5), 286-296. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/cod.12327</p>	<p>The Netherlands, Spain, Italy, Switzerland. Portugal, Belgium: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Assess whether sensitization to palladium and/or Ni associated with clinical variables consisting of exposure to different subsets of dental alloys and oral symptoms/complaints in six western European dermatology clinics. Explore possible differences in associations between monosensitization to both metals</p>	<p>Adults</p>

<p>Nicolae, A., Ames, H., & Quinonez, C. (2013). DA and U-Hg concentrations: a descriptive study. <i>BMC oral health</i>, 13, 44. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1472-6831-13-44</p>	<p>Canada: Cross sectional (national survey)</p>	<p>Determine overall U-Hg level in Canadian general population in relation to the no.DA surfaces</p>	<p>Adult and Children (Age 6-79)</p>
<p>Nuvulone 2023 Levels and determinants of urinary and blood metals in the geothermal area of Mt. Amiata in Tuscany (Italy)</p>	<p>Italy: Population cross-sectional</p>	<p>Evaluates extent of population exposure to metals and describe major individual and environmental determinants</p>	<p>Population: Adults (18-70)</p>
<p>Olms, C., Yahiaoui-Doktor, M., & Remmerbach Torsten, W. (2019). Contact allergies to dental materials. <i>SWISS DENTAL JOURNAL SSO – Science And Clinical Topics</i>, 129(7/8), 571-579. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.61872/sdj-2019-07-08-555</p>	<p>Germany: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Determine frequencies and symptoms of allergies to dental materials (dental allergies)</p>	<p>Adults (24-86)</p>
<p>Orlando Mark, S., Love, T., Harrington, D., Dziorny Adam, C., Shamlaye Conrad, F., Watson Gene, E., van Wijngaarden, E., Davidson Philip, W., & Myers Gary, J. (2023). The association of auditory function measures with low-level methylHg from oceanic fish consumption and Hg vapor from amalgam: The Seychelles Child Development Study Nutrition 1 Cohort. <i>Neurotoxicology</i>, 95, 46-55. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2022.12.010</p>	<p>USA: Prospective observational cohort</p>	<p>Determine influence of co-exposure to MeHg from maternal or childhood fish consumption and Hg^o from maternal or childhood amalgam in children. Associations with Hg exposure and auditory outcomes examined</p>	<p>Maternal exposure: Mother-infant pairs-302</p>
<p>Palkovicova, L., Ursinyova, M., Masanova, V., Yu, Z., & Hertz-Picciotto, I. (2008). Maternal amalgam dental fillings as the source of Hg exposure in developing fetus and newborn. <i>Journal of exposure science & environmental epidemiology</i>, 18(3), 326-331. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/sj.jes.7500606</p>	<p>Slovakia: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Assess relationship between maternal DA and exposure of fetus to Hg</p>	<p>Maternal exposure: Mother-child pairs (Mother- 18 to 42yrs;</p>

<p>Parajuli Rajendra, P., Goodrich Jaclyn, M., Chou, H.-N., Gruninger Stephen, E., Dolinoy Dana, C., Franzblau, A., & Basu, N. (2016). Genetic polymorphisms are associated with hair, blood, and U-Hg levels in the American Dental Association (ADA) study participants. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 149, 247-258. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2015.11.032</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Hypothesis:SNPs in genes may underline inter-individual differences in exposure biomarker concentrations</p>	<p>HCP: Dental professionals</p>
<p>Park, S.-B., Kim, E.-K., Sakong, J., & Park Eun, Y. (2023). Association between DA restoration and U-Hg concentrations among young women: a cross-sectional study. <i>Journal of Yeungnam medical science</i>, 40(4), 373-380. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.12701/jyms.2022.00955</p>	<p>South Korea: Cross sectional with control</p>	<p>Investigate association between DA fillings and U-Hg concentrations</p>	<p>Adults: Women (20-29yrs)</p>
<p>Parkin, K., Jane, A., & Pamphlett, R. (2018). A Comparison of Hg Exposure from Seafood Consumption and DA Fillings in People with and without Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS): An International Online Case-Control Study. <i>INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND PUBLIC HEALTH</i>, 15(12). https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15122874</p>	<p>Australia: Cross sectional [Case control]</p>	<p>Determine whether people with ALS more likely than controls without ALS to be exposed to higher levels of Hg from seafood/DA fillings</p>	<p>Adults-MA: ALS respondents: 61.5yrs (SD 9.2yrs, range 40–87yrs). Controls: 57.3yrs (SD 10.4yrs, range 40–89yrs), significant difference on t-testing (p<0.001)</p>
<p>Pawlas, N., Stromberg, U., Carlberg, B., Cerna, M., Harari, F., Harari, R., Horvat, M., Hrubá, F., Koppová, K., Krsková, A., Krsnik, M., Li, Y.-F., Lofmark, L., Lundh, T., Lundström, N.-G., Lyoussi, B., Markiewicz-Gorka, I., Mazej, D., Osredkar, J., Pawlas, K., Rentschler, G., Spevacková, V., Spiric, Z., Sundkvist, A., Tratnik Janja, S., Vadla, D., Zizi, S., Skerfving, S., & Bergdahl Ingvar, A. (2013). Cd, Hg and lead in the blood of urban women in Croatia, the Czech Republic, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, China, Ecuador and Morocco. <i>International journal of occupational medicine and environmental health</i>, 26(1), 58-72. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.2478/S13382-013-0071-9</p>	<p>Croatia, Czech republic, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, China, Ecuador, Morocco : Cross sectional</p>	<p>International comparison of blood levels of Cd, Pb and Hg of women in seven European & three non-European cities, and to identify determinants</p>	<p>Women (age: 46–62)</p>

<p>Pigatto Paolo, D., Minoia, C., Ronchi, A., Brambilla, L., Ferrucci Silvia, M., Spadari, F., Passoni, M., Somalvico, F., Bombeccari Gian, P., & Guzzi, G. (2013). Allergological and toxicological aspects in a multiple chemical sensitivity cohort. <i>Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity</i>, 2013, 356235. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2013/356235</p>	<p>Italy: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Measure Hg levels in human biological matrices. Determine outcome of allergic reactions to metals by using in vivo patch testing and/or in vitro lymphocyte transformation test to investigate association between Hg levels and cases of MCS</p>	<p>Adult MA 44.8 ± 11.2yrs</p>
<p>Pirard, C., Compere, S., Firquet, K., & Charlier, C. (2018). The current environmental levels of endocrine disruptors (Hg, Cd, organochlorine pesticides and PCBs) in a Belgian adult population and their predictors of exposure. <i>International Journal of Hygiene & Environmental Health</i>, 221(2), 211-222. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2017.10.010</p>	<p>Belgium: Cross sectional</p>	<p>1) Determine current exposure level of some EDC in Liege population, 2) assess temporal trends in exposure, 3) identify critical subpopulations in terms of exposure levels according to daily habits/demographic characteristics</p>	<p>Adult (18–69yrs old)</p>
<p>Pirard, C., Koppen, G., De Cremer, K., Van Overmeire, I., Govarts, E., Dewolf, M.-C., Van De Mierop, E., Aerts, D., Biot, P., Casteleyn, L., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Schwedler, G., Angerer, J., Koch Holger, M., Schindler Birgit, K., Castano, A., Esteban, M., Schoeters, G., Den Hond, E., Sepai, O., Exley, K., Horvat, M., Bloemen, L., Knudsen Lisbeth, E., Joas, R., Joas, A., Van Loco, J., & Charlier, C. (2014). Hair Hg and urinary Cd levels in Belgian children and their mothers within the framework of the COPHES/DEMOCOPHES projects. <i>The Science of the total environment</i>, 472, 730-740. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.11.028</p>	<p>Belgium: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Reports results for heavy metals measured in Belgian population participating to DEMOCOPHES project: Cd in urine and Hg hair. Urinary Cd and hair Hg compared with national and international studies, and multiple linear regression analyses to identify determinants of exposure to both biomarkers</p>	<p>Maternal exposure: Mother-child pairs: children (6–11yrs) and their mothers (≤45yrs)</p>
<p>Prokopowicz, A., Pawlas, N., Ochota, P., Szulą, M., Sobczak, A., & Pawlas, K. (2014). Blood Levels of Lead, Cd, and Hg in Healthy Women in their 50s in an Urban Area of Poland: A Pilot Study. <i>Polish Journal of Environmental Studies</i>, 23(1), 167-175. https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eih&AN=94198707&site=ehost-live</p>	<p>Poland: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Assess blood exposure levels to Pb, Cd, and Hg in 80 upper middle-aged women living in Wrocław, and identify environmental, sociodemographic, and lifestyle factors that may influence these</p>	<p>Adults: Women (50-59yrs)</p>

<p>Raap, U., Stiesch, M., Reh, H., Kapp, A., & Werfel, T. (2009). Investigation of contact allergy to dental metals in 206 patients. <i>Contact dermatitis</i>, 60(6), 339-343. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0536.2009.01524.x</p>	<p>Germany: Cross sectional</p>	<p>To analyse positive patch test reactions to metals (as their alloys or salts) used in dentistry together with clinical symptoms and possible relevance to dental fillings</p>	<p>Patients: 28 showed min.1 positive patch test reaction to dental metals. (=27, 96%; mean age SD: 48.2 15.8). Only 1 male patient (4%, aged 45yrs); 178 of 206 patients did not have any patch test reaction to dental metals. 137 patients female (mean age; SD: 41.5; 17.3)</p>
<p>Ramos, L., Cabral, R., & Gonçalo, M. (2014). Allergic contact dermatitis caused by acrylates and methacrylates – a 7-year study. <i>Contact Dermatitis</i>, 71(2), 102-107. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/cod.12266</p>	<p>Portugal: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Characterize ACD caused by (meth)acrylates, identify responsible allergens, and assess sensitivity of patch test with 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA) for diagnosis</p>	<p>Adults (22-68)</p>
<p>Richardson, G. M. (2014). Hg Exposure and Risks from DA in Canada: The Canadian Health Measures Survey 2007–2009. <i>Human & Ecological Risk Assessment</i>, 20(2), 433-447. https://doi.org/10.1080/10807039.2012.743433</p>	<p>Canada: Retrospective observational</p>	<p>Update assessment of exposure to and risks from Hg0 from DA in Canadian population</p>	<p>Mix: Children aged 6 to 11yrs; Teens aged 12 to 19yrs; Adults aged 20 to 64yrs; Seniors aged ≥65yrs</p>
<p>Rothwell Janet, A., & Boyd Paul, J. (2008). Amalgam dental fillings and hearing loss. <i>Comment in: Int J Audiol</i>. 2010 Jan;49(1):69-70 PMID: 20001448 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/20001448], 47(12), 770-776. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14992020802311224</p>	<p>UK: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Investigated effects of amalgam dental fillings on auditory thresholds</p>	<p>Adults: women age 40 to 45</p>
<p>Ryo, K., Ito, A., Takatori, R., Tai, Y., Tokunaga, J., Arikawa, K., Yamada, T., Shinpo, K., Yasuda, H., & Saito, I. (2010). Correlation Between Hg Concentrations in Hair and DA Fillings. <i>ANTI-AGING MEDICINE</i>, 7(3), 14-17. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3793/jaam.7.14</p>	<p>Japan: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Examine association between DA fillings and hair-Hg</p>	<p>Adults (26-65)</p>

<p>Sekovanic, A., Piasek, M., Orct, T., Sulimanec, G., Antonija, Matek, S., Marijana, Stasenko, S., & Jurasovic, J. (2020). Hg Exposure Assessment in Mother-Infant Pairs from Continental and Coastal Croatia. <i>Biomolecules</i>, 10(6). https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.3390/biom10060821</p>	<p>Croatia: Cross-sectional study with comparison</p>	<p>Determine Hg and Se concentrations in maternal and fetal samples after childbirth, and compare between study participants from coastal and continental areas with presumed different seafood/fish consumption and related Hg exposure</p>	<p>Mother-infant pairs Mother -Continental 29.4 ± 4.64; Coastal 29.3 ± 4.76</p>
<p>Sharma Brij, M., Komprdova, K., Lorinczova, K., Kuta, J., Pribylova, P., Scheringer, M., Sebejova, L., Piler, P., Zvonar, M., & Klanova, J. (2024). Human biomonitoring of essential and toxic trace elements (heavy metals and metalloids) in urine of children, teenagers, and young adults from a Central European Cohort in the Czech Republic. <i>Journal of exposure science & environmental epidemiology</i>. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41370-024-00724-4</p>	<p>Czech Republic: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Present study analyzed urinary concentrations of 14 trace elements (As, Cd, Co, chromium, Cu, Hg, Mn, molybdenum, Ni, lead, antimony, selenium, thallium, and Zn) and exposure determinants in 711 children and young adults</p>	<p>Children (10–11yrs), teenagers (12–17yrs), and young adults (18–37 years)</p>
<p>Sherman Laura, S., Blum Joel, D., Franzblau, A., & Basu, N. (2013). New insight into biomarkers of human Hg exposure using naturally occurring Hg stable isotopes. <i>Environmental science & technology</i>, 47(7), 3403-3409. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/es305250z</p>	<p>USA: Cross sectional</p>	<p>We undertook this study to further investigate whether Hg stable isotope ratios in human hair and urine can be used to quantify exposure to Hg⁰ (g) and MeHg more accurately than measurement of total Hg concentrations. We measured Hg isotope ratios in hair and urine from a group of North American dental professionals</p>	<p>Dental professionals (NR)</p>
<p>Stetvold H, Svendsen K, Aas O, Syverson T, Hilt B. Neuropsychological function and past exposure to metallic Hg in female dental workers. <i>Scand J Psychol</i> 2012;53:136e43.</p>	<p>Norway: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Investigate if dental personnel previously exposed to metallic Hg developed cognitive disturbances</p>	<p>Female adult dental personnel (<70yrs)</p>

<p>Snoj Tratnik Janja, S., Falnoga, I., Trdin, A., Mazej, D., Fajon, V., Višnjevec Ana, M., Kobal Alfred, B., Osredkar, J., Briški Alenka, S., Krsnik, M., Neubauer, D., Kodrič, J., Stropnik, S., Gosar, D., Musek Petra, L., Marc, J., Mlakar Simona, J., Petrovič, O., Vlašič-Cicvarič, I., Prpič, I., Milardovič, A., Nišević Jelena, R., Vuković, D., Fišić, E., Špirić, Z., & Horvat, M. (2016). Prenatal Hg exposure, neurodevelopment and apolipoprotein E genetic polymorphism. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 152, 375-385. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2016.08.035</p>	<p>Slovenia: Prospective cohort study</p>	<p>Evaluate association between prenatal exposure to Hg (Hg) and neurodevelopment of the child, taking into account genetic polymorphism of apolipoprotein E (ApoE) and other relevant confounders</p>	<p>Children- maternal exposure</p>
<p>Snoj, T., Janja, Falnoga, I., Mazej, D., Kocman, D., Fajon, V., Jagodic, M., Stajniko, A., Trdin, A., Slejkovec, Z., Jeran, Z., Osredkar, J., Seseek-Briski, A., Krsnik, M., Kobal Alfred, B., Kononenko, L., & Horvat, M. (2019). Results of the first national human biomonitoring in Slovenia: Trace elements in men and lactating women, predictors of exposure and reference values. <i>International journal of hygiene and environmental health</i>, 222(3), 563-582. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2019.02.008</p>	<p>Slovenia: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Estimate trace elements' levels and geographical variations to identify sources of exposures and set national reference values</p>	<p>Mothers</p>
<p>Stahlnacke, K., & Soderfeldt, B. (2012). Factors related to persons with health problems attributed to dental filling materials--part one in a triangular study on 65 and 75yrs old Swedes. <i>Swedish dental journal</i>, 36(4), 195-206. http://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&PAGE=reference&D=med9&NEWS=N&AN=23421310</p>	<p>Sweden: Cross-sectional with comparison group</p>	<p>Investigate perceived oral health in persons having problems with dental filling materials in Swedish population, and their reception from dental care personnel.</p>	<p>Patients: Adults-older adults (65-75yrs)</p>
<p>Stejskal et al (2015) Increased frequency of delayed type hypersensitivity to metals in patients with connective tissue disease</p>	<p>Sweden: Cross-sectional with control group</p>	<p>Examine incidence of delayed type hypersensitivity (Type IV allergy) to metals</p>	<p>Adults with connective tissue disease (systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis or sjorgens's syndrome)</p>
<p>Stejskal, V., Ockert, K., & Bjorklund, G. (2013). Metal-induced inflammation triggers fibromyalgia in metal-allergic patients. <i>Neuro endocrinology letters</i>, 34(6), 559-565. http://ovidsp.ovid.com/ovidweb.cgi?T=JS&PAGE=reference&D=med10&NEWS=N&AN=24378456</p>	<p>NR: Before and After</p>	<p>Sudy frequency and clinical relevance of metal allergy in FM patients</p>	<p>Adults: Female Fibromyalgia M (mean age (47.6yrs, range 34-66yrs)</p>
<p>Sun, Y.-H., Nfor Oswald, N., Huang, J.-Y., & Liaw, Y.-P. (2015). Association between DA fillings and Alzheimer's disease: a population-based cross-sectional study in Taiwan. <i>Comment in: Alzheimers Res Ther.</i> 2016;8:1 PMID: 26776763 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26776763], 7(1), 65. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13195-015-0150-1</p>	<p>Taiwan: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Evaluate association between DA and Alzheimer's disease in Taiwanese population aged 65 and older</p>	<p>Adults (65yrs and older)</p>

<p>Svendsen K, Syversen T, Melø I, Hilt B. Historical exposure to Hg among Norwegian dental personnel. <i>Scand J Work Environ Health</i> 2010;36: 231e41</p>	<p>Norway: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>1) Describe Norwegian dental personnel's exposure to Hg during last 50yrs, 2) develop model for scoring reflecting individual cumulative exposure, 3) relate calculated score to earlier measured U-Hg</p>	<p>Adults (dental personnel)</p>
<p>Szklarek, M., & Kostka, T. (2019). The impact of the use of amalgam in dental treatment on the prevalence of restless legs syndrome in older people. <i>MEDYCYNA PRACY</i>, 70(1), 9-16. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.13075/mp.5893.00749</p>	<p>UK-Wales: Cross sectional</p>	<p>Study prevalence of RLS and its connection to the presence of amalgam fillings</p>	<p>Adults (60-97yrs)</p>
<p>Tillberg, A., Mårell, L., Berglund, A., & Eriksson, N. (2008). Replacement of restorations in subjects with symptoms associated with dental restorations;: a follow-up study. <i>EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF ORAL SCIENCES</i>, 116(4), 362-368. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0722.2008.00553.x</p>	<p>Sweden: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Assess long-term development of symptoms and social consequences among patients referred for diagnosis and treatment of symptoms believed to be related to dental-restorative materials</p>	<p>Adults</p>
<p>Tillberg, A., Stenberg, B., & Berglund, A. (2009). Reactions to resin-based dental materials in patients--type, time to onset, duration, and consequence of the reaction. <i>Contact dermatitis</i>, 61(6), 313-319. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0536.2009.01590.x</p>	<p>Sweden: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Determine types of side-effects occurring and for how long they lasted in a group of patients with side-effects assessed to be caused by resin-based materials</p>	<p>Adults</p>
<p>Ting, S., Nguyen, J., Palmer, A., Rosemary, N., & A, M. (2023). Contact sensitisation in oral lichen planus: An Australian perspective. <i>Contact dermatitis</i>, 89(5), 335-344. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/cod.14366</p>	<p>Australia: Retrospective Observational: Case Control study</p>	<p>Evaluate relevant contact sensitisers in OLP</p>	<p>Patients with oral pathology</p>
<p>Torgerson Rochelle, R., Davis Mark, D. P., Bruce Alison, J., Farmer Sara, A., & Rogers Roy, S. (2007). Contact allergy in oral disease. <i>Journal Of The American Academy Of Dermatology</i>, 57(2), 315-321. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2007.04.017</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional (with retrospective review to identify participants with oral disease/symptoms?)</p>	<p>Determine prevalence of contact allergy to flavorings, preservatives, dental acrylates, medications, and metals in patients with oral disease.</p>	<p>Children and adults (12-90yrs old)</p>

<p>Trdin, A., Falnoga, I., Fajon, V., Zivkovic, I., Snoj, T., Janja, Prpic, I., Spiric, Z., & Horvat, M. (2019). Hg speciation in meconium and associated factors. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 179(Pt A), 108724. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108724</p>	<p>Slovenia: Retrospective Observational</p>	<p>The present study aims to speciate Hg in meconium samples (N=488) from Slovenian and Croatian new-borns prenatally exposed to low levels of methyl-Hg (MeHg) from maternal seafood intake and to Hg⁰ from maternal DA fillings.</p>	<p>Pregnant women and their newborns</p>
<p>Trzcinka-Ochocka, M., Gazewski, A., & Brodzka, R. (2007). Exposure to Hg vapors in dental workers in Poland. <i>International journal of occupational medicine and environmental health</i>, 20(2), 147-153. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.2478/v10001-007-0017-1</p>	<p>Poland: Cross-sectional study with a control group</p>	<p>Assess effect of low-level exposure to Hg (Hg) vapor from amalgam fillings among dental surgery staff in Łódź, Poland</p>	<p>Workers employed in dental surgeries and a control group of white collar workers with no or few amalgam fillings</p>
<p>Tschudi-Madsen, H., Kjeldsberg, M., Natvig, B., Ihlebaek, C., Straand, J., & Bruusgaard, D. (2014). Medically unexplained conditions considered by patients in general practice. <i>Family practice</i>, 31(2), 156-163. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cmt081</p>	<p>Norway: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Explore whether patients consider they may suffer from unexplained conditions and explore associations between these concerns and symptom load, life stressors and socio-demographic factors</p>	<p>Patients</p>
<p>Tucek, M., Busova, M., Cejchanova, M., Schlenker, A., & Kapitan, M. (2020). Exposure to Hg from DA: actual contribution for risk assessment. <i>Central European journal of public health</i>, 28(1), 40-43. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.21101/cejph.a5965</p>	<p>Czech Republic: Cross sectional with a comparison group</p>	<p>Health risk assessment of occupational exposure to Hg in dentists working with DA and exposure to Hg in persons treated with amalgam dental restorationS</p>	<p>Dentists+patients</p>

<p>Ursinyova, M., Uhnakova, I., Serbin, R., Masanova, V., Husekova, Z., & Wsolova, L. (2012). The relation between human exposure to Hg and thyroid hormone status. <i>Biological trace element research</i>, 148(3), 281-291. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12011-012-9382-0</p>	<p>Slovakia: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Investigate total Hg (THg) and methylHg (MeHg) exposure of 75 mother-child pairs in relation to thyroid hormone status (thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), triiodothyronine (T3), free triiodothyronine (fT3), thyroxine (T4), and free thyroxine (fT4))</p>	<p>Mother-child pairs</p>
<p>Vervliet, P., De Nys, S., Duca Radu, C., Boonen, I., Godderis, L., Elskens, M., Van Landuyt Kirsten, L., & Covaci, A. (2023). Degradation products of resin-based materials detected in saliva in vivo. <i>Clinical oral investigations</i>, 27(12), 7189-7198. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00784-023-05075-2</p>	<p>Belgium: Before and after study</p>	<p>Quantitatively and qualitatively monitor release of parent compounds and degradation products in saliva from patients undergoing multiple restorations.</p>	<p>Patients (n=5)</p>
<p>Visalli, G., Baluce, B., La Maestra, S., Micale Rosanna, T., Cingano, L., De Flora, S., & Di Pietro, A. (2013). Genotoxic damage in the oral mucosa cells of subjects carrying restorative dental fillings. <i>Comment in: Arch Toxicol.</i> 2013 Jun;87(6):1155-6 PMID: 23563989 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23563989], 87(1), 179-187. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00204-012-0915-2</p>	<p>Italy: Cross-sectional study</p>	<p>to evaluate the potential local genotoxicity of dental fillings by testing oral mucosa cells. The mucosa cells, being directly exposed to dental compounds, are the first-pass target of the potential harmful effects of these iatrogenic xenobiotics. In the present biomonitoring study, genotoxicity assessment of dental compounds was performed in subjects carrying restorative dental fillings and their matched controls by using both the comet assay and the MN test.</p>	<p>Adults (students of Medical Faculty)</p>
<p>Vogel, N., Murawski, A., Schmied-Tobies Maria, I. H., Rucic, E., Doyle, U., Kampfe, A., Hora, C., Hildebrand, J., Schafer, M., Drexler, H., Goen, T., & Kolossa-Gehring, M. (2021). Lead, Cd, Hg, and chromium in urine and blood of children and adolescents in Germany-Human biomonitoring results of the German Environmental Survey 2014-2017 (GerES V). <i>International journal of hygiene and environmental health</i>, 237, 113822. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113822</p>	<p>Germany : Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Describe current internal exposure of children and adolescents to lead, Cd, Hg, and chromium, and testing possible exposure determinants for internal exposure in bivariate analyses with national population representative, cross sectional data on human internal exposure to environmental chemicals and its sources</p>	<p>Children (3-17 yrs)</p>

<p>Vollset, M., Iszatt, N., Enger, O., Gjengedal Elin Lovise, F., & Eggesbo, M. (2019). Concentration of Hg, Cd, and lead in breast milk from Norwegian mothers: Association with dietary habits, amalgam and other factors. <i>The Science of the total environment</i>, 677, 466-473. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.04.252</p>	<p>Norway: Retrospective Observational</p>	<p>Hg (Hg), Cd (Cd), and lead (Pb) are of great concern for food safety and infants are especially sensitive to exposure to the maternal body burden. Quantified elements in breast milk from Norwegian mothers and determined association with dietary habits, maternal amalgam fillings, and smoking</p>	<p>Adults (mothers)</p>
<p>Woods James, S., Armel Sarah, E., Fulton Denise, I., Allen, J., Wessels, K., Simmonds, P. L., Granpeesheh, D., Mumper, E., Bradstreet, J. J., Echeverria, D., Heyer Nicholas, J., & Rooney James, P. K. (2010). Urinary porphyrin excretion in neurotypical and autistic children. <i>Environmental Health Perspectives</i>, 118(10), 1450-1457. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1289/ehp.0901713</p>	<p>USA: cross-sectional with control</p>	<p>This study was designed to measure and compare urinary porphyrin concentration in neurotypical (NT) children and same-age children with autism, and to examine the association between porphyrin levels and past or current Hg exposure in children with autism</p>	<p>children 2-12 yrs</p>
<p>Woods, M. D. Martin, B. G. Leroux et al. Contribution of dental amalgam to urinary mercury excretion in children,” <i>Environmental Health Perspectives</i>, vol. 115, no. 10, pp. 1527–1531, 2007</p>	<p>USA: RCT</p>	<p>Evaluate urinary mercury in children 8–18 years of age in relation to no.amalgam surfaces and time since placement over 7-year course of amalgam treatment</p>	<p>Patient: Children (8-10 years)</p>
<p>Wranova, K., Cejchanova, M., Spevakova, V., Korunova, V., Vobecky, M., & Spevacek, V. (2009). Hg and methylHg in hair of selected groups of Czech population. <i>Central European journal of public health</i>, 17(1), 36-40. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.21101/cejph.a3513</p>	<p>Czech Republic: Cross-sectional Study with a comparison group</p>	<p>Validated analytical method with AMA 254 spectrometer used for the determination of inorganic Hg and methylHg species in hair of dentists, workers in fish industry and professionally non-exposed adults</p>	<p>Dentists, workers in fish industry and professionally non-exposed adults</p>
<p>Xu, W., Park Sung, K., Gruninger Stephen, E., Charles, S., Franzblau, A., Basu, N., & Goodrich Jaclyn, M. (2023). Associations between Hg exposure with blood pressure and lipid levels: A cross-sectional study of dental professionals. <i>Environmental Research</i>, 220, 115229. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.115229</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Examine associations between Hg exposure (both elemental and methylHg) and blood pressure+cholesterol and triglyceride levels.</p>	<p>HCP: Dental professionals</p>

<p>Yin, L., Lin, S., Summers Anne, O., Roper, V., Campen Matthew, J., & Yu, X. (2021). Children with Amalgam Dental Restorations Have Significantly Elevated Blood and U-Hg Levels. Erratum in: Toxicol Sci. 2022 Feb 28;186(1):174 PMID: 35107165 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/35107165], 184(1), 104-126. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfab108</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional Study with comparison group</p>	<p>Examine data from two most recent NHANES on 14 181subjects to assess contributions of seafood consumption versus AMG to blood total Hg (THg), inorganic Hg (IHg), and methyl Hg (MeHg) and to urine creatinine corrected Hg (UTHg)</p>	<p>Adults & children 1-66+</p>
<p>Yin, L., Yu, K., Lin, S., Song, X., & Yu, X. (2016). Associations of blood Hg, inorganic Hg, methyl Hg and bisphenol A with dental surface restorations in the U.S. population, NHANES 2003-2004 and 2010-2012. Ecotoxicology and environmental safety, 134P1, 213-225. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2016.09.001</p>	<p>USA: Cross-sectional study with comparison group</p>	<p>Use NHANES data to examine association between DSR and blood Hg, IHg, MeHg)and urinary BPA</p>	<p>Adults & children 3-66+</p>
<p>Zarra, T., & Lambrianidis, T. (2013). Occupational ocular accidents amongst Greek endodontists: a national questionnaire survey. International endodontic journal, 46(8), 710-719. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/iej.12048</p>	<p>Greece: Cross-sectional</p>	<p>Investigate amongst Greek endodontists, incidence of ocular accidents during practice, circumstances associated with them, therapeutic measures taken after accidents, compliance with use of eye protection and eye care behaviour.</p>	<p>HCP: endodontist dentists</p>
<p>Zhang, X., Gelderblom Hans, R., Zierold, K., & Reichart Peter, A. (2007). Morphological findings and energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis of oral amalgam tattoos. Comment in: Micron. 2007;38(6):694-5; author reply 696 PMID: 17398102 [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/17398102], 38(5), 543-548. https://doi.org/https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.micron.2006.07.020</p>	<p>Germany: Cross sectional study</p>	<p>Scrutinize state of incorporated amalgam with particular interest in: 1) the tissue distribution of metallic substances, 2) specific association of electron-dense deposits with intra- and extracellular structures and 3) element composition using X-ray microanalysis</p>	<p>Patients (n=15) with 17 pigmentations (5 patients, ATs occurred in the maxillary gingival, while 10 patients showed ATs in the mandibular gingiva and alveolar mucosa (2 patients presented 2 ATs)</p>

2-HEMA=2-Hydroxyethyl Methacrylate=2-HEMA, ABL=Alveolar Bone Loss, Ag=Silver, ALS=Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis, AMG=Amalgams, AMI=Acute, Myocardial Infarction, AOR=Adj Methacryloxypropoxy Phenylpropane, bisHPP=Bishydroxypropoxyphenylpropane, BMI=Body Mass Index, BMS=Burning Mouth Syndrome, BPA=Bisphenol A, CA=Chloralkal, Cd=Cadmium, CNS=Central Nervous System, Co=Cobalt, Cr=Chromium, CRR=Composite Resin Restorations, CT=Can't Tell, Cu=Copper, D=Day, DA=DA, DAFS=Dental Amalgam Filling Surface, DB DSR=Dental Surface Restorations, DT=Dental Technician, EA=Ethyl Acrylate (EA), EDC=Endocrine Disruptors, EGDMA=Ethylene glycol Dimethacrylate, EHS=Electromagnetic Hypersensitivity, fT3=Free Triiodothyronine, GBM=Glomerular Basement Membrane, GER-ES=German Environmental Survey, GI=Gingival Index, GV=Guidance Values, HBM=Human Biomonitoring, HBM Ratio, hr=Hour, Ihg=Inorganic Mercury, Ir=Iridium, LBW=Low Birth Weight, LH=Luteinizing Hormone, Li=Lithium, M/T=Missing Teeth, MB=Maternal Blood, MCS=Multiple Chemical Sensitivity, N=No, NA=Not Applicable, NAG=N-acetyl-beta-D-Glucosaminidase, NHANES=National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, Ni=Nickel, NKT=Natural Killer T cells, NR=Not reported, Pb=Lead, PBI=Papillary Bleeding Index, PCB=Polychlorinated Biphenyls, PCDD/PCDF=Polychlorinated-p-Dioxins/Polychlorinated-p-Furans, Pd=Palladium, PI=Plaque Index, PSI=Periodontitis, RR=Relative Risk, RV=Reference Values, RV95=Reference Value 95, Sb=Antimony, SBP=Systolic Blood Pressure, SD=Standard Deviation, Se=Selenium, SHBG=Sex Hormone Binding Globulin, TEGDMA=Triethylene glycol Dimethacrylate, TEM=Transmission Electron Microscope, THFMA=Tetrahydrofurfuryl Methacrylate, THg=Total Mercury, THS=Thyroid Hormone Status, Ti=Titanium, U=Uranium, U-BPA=Urinary-BPA, USA=United States of America, V=Vanadium, wk=Week, WTE=Waste To Energy, Y=Yes, yrs=Years,

Dental material -health impact link study primary focus? (Y/N) Dental materials evaluated/implicated (intervention); Comparator	Exposure or Broad health impact category: Specific outcome/s measured	Length of follow up (Length of time post restoration)	Summary of main findings (copied from abstract)
N: Acrylic monomers: used in prostheses, dental composite resins, dentin bonding materials, glass ionomers; NA	Allergy: Allergic reaction to acrylic monomer	read tests 2/3 times [on D2-(D3)-D4/5/6] depending on day of application	Dental professionals most commonly exposed to 2-HEMA, TREGDMA, and bis-GMA. 8 dentists and 12 dental nurses allergic to 2-HEMA. Remaining dentist positive to bis-GMA and other epoxy acrylates. Remaining 3 dental nurses reacted to DEGDA or TREGDA, but not to monofunctional and multifunctional methacrylates. Dental technicians mainly exposed and sensitized to MMA and EGDMA. 1 technician reacted only to 2-HEMA, another EMA+EA
N: Acrylic monomers: used in prostheses, dental composite resins, dentin bonding materials, glassionomers; NA	Allergy: Allergic reaction to acrylic monomer	read the tests two or three times, depending on the day of application (D2, D3 and D4; D2, D3 and D6; or D2 and D5)	Most commonly positive allergens: EGDMA, 2-HPMA, DEGDA. Concomitant reaction patterns suggest exposure to methacrylates may induce cross-reactivity to acrylates. Exposure to acrylates usually does not=cross-allergy methacrylates
N (24 patients-3 related to dentistry): Dental composite resins: bis-GMA and methacrylates; Dental products: 2-HEMA, TREGDMA, bis-GMA, UEDMA; NA	Allergy: Allergic reaction to epoxy (meth)acrylates	CT	24 patients allergic reaction to min.1 of studied epoxy (meth)acrylates, but specific exposure found only in 5 patients: 2xbis-GMA allergies from dental products, 2xbis-GA allergies from UV-curable printing inks, 1xbis-GA allergy from anaerobic glue. 25% of patients negative to DGEBA epoxy resin
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Daily intake of Hg (total Hg blood concentrations)	CT	Toxicokinetic modelling of blood levels gave higher daily intake values of Hg compared vs FFQ and had a wider range of estimates

Y. Borderline: Hg; NA	Allergy: Lichen series patch test	Patch test removed by patient on D2, read on D3+D7	Of 19 patients with OLL next to amalgam fillings, 78.9 % sensitised to inorganic Hg, 33.3 % positive on D10 or D17 only . They were not read on D7
Y: Amalgam: divided into five groups (G1–G5) based on ages of class II amalgam restorations (2, 4, 7, 10, and > 10yrs); NA	Oral health: PI, GI, OH, ABL	See Dental materials	Periodontal parameters of examined groups demonstrated low and intermediate scores from 25% to 41% for ABL, 1.1 to 1.5 for PI, and 1.2 to 1.5 for GI. G4 and G5 had highest scores for three parameters (PI, GI, and ABL); $p < 0.001$. Overhangs rate varied, G1 and G3 had highest rate ($p < 0.037$)
See Albakry 2021: See Albakry 2021; See Albakry 2021	Oral health: See Albakry 2021	See Albakry 2021	Mean HbA1c ranged from 7.8% to 11%. Groups' mean diabetes durations (\pm SD): 2.1 (SD 0.33), 4.3 (SD 0.36), 9 (SD 1.2), 12.5 (SD 0.9), and 12 (SD 0.84). Periodontal scores were high (worse periodontal parameters), range: 42% to 59.5% ABL, 2.45 to 2.95 PI, and 2.25 to 2.8 GI. Highest scores: G4 and G5 ($p < 0.001$). Highest rate of overhangs recorded G4 ($p < 0.001$)

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure	NR	Hg levels in mothers and respective infants relatively low. DA fillings and fish consumption main predictors maternal Hg exposure. Maternal hair/urine Hg strongest predictors infant exposure. No association between Hg breast milk and Hg in infant urine
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Female blood level: Hg, Cd and lead	NA?	RV95s for Hg, Cd and lead in Al-Kharj (Riyadh) blood: 5.9 (1.6) µg/l, 1.4 (1.9) µg/l and 4.3 (4.8) µg/dl. RV95s for U-Hg, Cd and lead in Riyadh samples expressed in µg/l (µg/g creatinine): 2.5 (1.9), 1.2 (0.96) and 14 (10.8). Values in both matrices remained high when factors such as secondhand smoking, DA, and/or fish consumption excluded. RV95s for metals in blood generally higher than other countries, except for Hg in Riyadh samples, which was also 4-fold lower than in Al-Kharj. Due to time lag between two studies, and since AlKharj study conducted 13yrs ago, most recent RV95s derived from Riyadh study recommended for Saudi women living in Central region. RV95s for U-Hg and Cd comparable to other countries, but lead requires closer attention
Y: Amalgam; No amalgam filling	Oral health/Exposure: Urinary, hair, toenail Hg. Oral health problems (Bleeding gum, meallic taste, Stomatitis, Aphthous ulcer, fool breath, white patches, gum pigmentation, burning mouth sensation ulcer of gum/tongue, bone loss around teeth, other)	NR	Children with amalgam (N=106) had significantly higher UHg-C levels than children without (N=76), means of 3.763 µg/g creatinine versus 3.457 µg/g creatinine, (P=0.019). Similar for UHg (P=0.01) and HHg, means of 0.614 µg/g (N=97) for children with amalgam versus 0.242 µg/g (N=74) for those without amalgam fillings (P=0). Not significant relationship between NHg and amalgam-without amalgam (0.222 µg/g, N=61) vs with (0.163 µg/g, N=101), (P=0.069). Adjusting for confounders, multiple logistic regression: levels of UHg-C and HHg were 2.047 and 5.396 times higher, in children with DA vs those without (P<0.01). Significant inverse relationship between NHg levels and DA fillings (P=0.003). This study showed some evidence amalgam-associated Hg exposure might be related with symptoms of oral health e..g aphthous ulcer, white patches, and burning-mouth sensation

N: Amalgam; NA	Health NS/Exposure: Hg maternal hair, breast milk, maternal blood; Hg child's hair, urine; urinary creatinine	NA	Mothers Hg levels and respective infants relatively low, but results consistent with other studies indicating DA fillings and fish consumption were main predictors of maternal Hg exposure. Among several biomarkers of Hg exposure, Hg levels maternal hair and urine strongest predictors of infant exposure. Lack of association between Hg in breast milk and Hg in infant urine and hair suggested infants were exposed to Hg predominately during pregnancy not breastfeeding
Y: Amalgam; No amalgam filling	Renal/Exposure: U-Hg, renal and oxidative stress biomarkers	NR	Multiple regression analyses: excretion urinary NAG significantly associated with DA fillings ($\beta=0.149$, $P=0.03$) and levels of UHg-C ($\beta=0.531$, $P=0$), with interaction between the two ($P=0$). The increase in urinary NAG in relation to UHg-C levels had dose-effect pattern. Lowest observed effect seen at UHg-C levels above 1.452 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine, lower than previously reported. $\alpha 1$ -MG negatively associated with DA fillings ($\beta=-0.270$, $P=0$), but positively with UHg-C levels ($\beta=0.393$, $P=0$). 7 children without, and one child with, DA fillings with urinary $\alpha 1$ -MG levels above reference limit of >7 mg/g creatinine. Hg affected excretion of urinary 8-OHdG in a dose-related pattern mostly associated with long-term exposure to low Hg levels. Urinary NAG levels positively associated with urinary MDA levels ($\beta=0.516$, $P=0$) but not 8-OHdG ($\beta=0.134$, $P=0.078$) after adjustment for potential confounders. Both UHg-C and DA fillings remained predictors of NAG model. Our data provide evidence low exposure to Hg from DA fillings exerts effect on kidney tubular functions in children. Oxidative stress may influence mechanism. Study results suggest urinary NAG most sensitive of investigated renal biomarkers
Y: Amalgam; NA	Neurological/Exposure: U-Hg, MS, tremor	Baseline, first follow up 6 months, second follow up 12months.	Children with $>!$ amalgam-filled TS exhibited significantly higher creatinine-adjusted U-Hg concentrations than those without, in all three survey periods ($P < 0.001$). The results for the current and cumulative amalgam-filled TS significantly correlated with those for the current and cumulative creatinine-adjusted U-Hg concentration, respectively, in all surveys ($P < 0.001$). In the repeated-measures mixed model analysis, current and cumulative amalgam-filled TS significantly related to current and cumulative creatinine-adjusted U-Hg concentration, respectively ($P < 0.001$).

Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: U-hg	Baseline, first follow up 6 months, second follow up 12months	Children with >1 amalgam-filled TS exhibited significantly higher creatinine-adjusted U-Hg concentrations vs those without (p<0.001). Current and cumulative amalgam-filled TS significantly correlated with those for current and cumulative creatinine-adjusted U-Hg concentration (p<0.001)
N: Amalgam vs NA	Exposure: kidney concentrations of Cd, Hg, and Pb	NR	Kidney Hg increased 6% for every additional amalgam surface, but not associated with fish consumption
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: U-Hg levels from 1995 - 2018, whole blood Hg levels from 2001- 2010	NR	Decrease (approx. 86% urine total daily Hg excretion from 1995 (0.76 µg/L) to 2018 (0.11 µg/L) (n=10,069), approx. 57% blood concentrations Hg from 2001 (1.76 µg/L) to 2010 (0.77 µg/L) (n=4085)). Only few values exceeded toxicologically derived health based guidance value HBM I for blood and urine, with exceedances decreasing over time in line with general trend. Factors mostly influencing Hg excretion: DA, fish and seafood consumption. Besides other factors (e.g. age and sex), airborne Hg exposure appears to be a low but evident influencing factor in Germany
N: Amalgam; NA	Pregnancy outcomes/Exposure: Maternal U-Hg/ neonate cord blood Hg; LBW and PTB	Delivery	No association between maternal exposure Hg, and LBW or PTB

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Urinary and blood: Cd, lead, Hg. GerES III: precious metals (gold and platinum), GerES IV: Ni and uranium	NR	U-Hg decreased because in Germany no longer recommended to use amalgam fillings for children
Y-borderline: Amalgam; NA	CVD/Exposure: S-Hg and mortality, AMI, or stroke	32yrs follow up	HR adjusted only for age: strong inverse associations between baseline S-Hg and total mortality [highest quartile: HR 0.76; 95% CI 0.59–0.97], incident AMI (HR 0.56; CI 0.34–0.93), and fatal AMI (HR 0.31; CI 0.15–0.66). Adjustment for potential confounding factors, especially dental health, strongly impacted risk estimates-after adjustment, only reduced risk fatal AMI SS
Y: Composite-dental polymer-based materials ; Without dental polymer-based fillings	Exposure: BPA levels: saliva/urine	Min. 7 days	Saliva BPA concentration very low. In composite group, 8/20 samples detectable concentrations BPA. Control group, 3/20 samples detectable concentrations BPA. Concentration of unconjugated BPA slightly higher in composite (p=0.044) vs control
Y: Composite-dental polymer-based materials ; NA	Exposure: BPA levels: saliva/urine	CT	SS increase salivary BPA concentration directly after placement of dental polymer-based restorations. Following placement, concentration of BPA decreased exponentially with time. 1wk after treatment BPA level in saliva only marginally higher than before treatment. In urine, no SS change of BPA concentration detected

Y: Amalgam vs CR vs Gold	Exposure: total-Hg and I-Hg: Blood, brain (occipital lobe cortex), pituitary, thyroid, abdominal muscle and toenails	NR	Median concentrations of MeHg (total-Hg minus I-Hg) and I-Hg in blood 2.2 and 1.0 µg/L, and in occipital lobe cortex 4 and 5 µg/kg, respectively. Significant correlation between MeHg in blood and occipital cortex. Total-Hg toenails correlated with MeHg in both blood and occipital lobe. I-Hg in blood and occipital cortex, as well as total-Hg in pituitary and thyroid strongly associated with no.DA surfaces at time of death
N: Amalgam; Composite	Immune function: Micronucleus number	NA	Study participants with high no. missing teeth (M/T index, p=0.037), below-average PBM (p=0.032) and periodontal status, respectively (PSI, p=0.042) possessed higher micronucleus number in comparison with restored dental conditions. Proband with composite restorations displayed higher MN rate (p=0.006) vs those with amalgam. No significant relation with prosthetic status (p=0.075). An adjustment was made according to alcohol and tobacco. Subgingival plaque and synthetic dental materials in addition to chronic alcohol and tobacco consumption might have genotoxic relevance in oral cavity
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Measurement of metal in urine/blood	NR Population sample living in area min. 5 yrs	Metal concentrations comparable with RVs reported in other countries, except for slightly higher As, Be, Ir, Pd, Pt, Rh, and Tl levels. Smoking was associated with Cd; age with Pb; drinking bottled water with As and Cd; consumption of fish with As and Hg; amalgams with Hg and Sn; dental restorations with Pd and Pt; use of jewelry with Co and Rh, and piercing with Ni. While HQs for urine Cd, Hg, Tl and blood Pb suggested that adverse effects were unlikely, the HQ value raised the question of whether additive interactions of these metals could produce health concern

<p>N (Fillings not main focus but all dentistry): Amalgam; Seven groups (n=15 per group). Group 1: patients with metal-porcelain fixed crowns on dental implants; Group 2: patients with metal-</p>	<p>Genotoxicity/Exposure: : Concentration of metal ions in buccal cells (Al27, Ti47, V51, Cr52, Mn55, Fe56, Co59, Ni60, Cu63, Zn66, Pd105, Ag107, Sn118, Pt195, Au197, Pb208 and Hg200). Genotoxic damage in buccal cells (cells with: micronuclei, nuclear</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>Group 5 highest concentration of metal ions parts/billion (Ti, Co, Ni, Zn, Pd, Sn, and Pb) followed by Group 3 (V, Cr, and Mn). Group 6 highest presence of Hg. No signs genotoxic damage found in any group</p>
<p>N: Amalgam; No filling</p>	<p>Exposure: Hg, Pb & Cd levels in the urine</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>Geometric means for total Hg, Pb and Cd were 1.23, 1.11 and 0.25 g/g creatinine, respectively. Pb and Hg > general population in USA and Germany, whereas Cd was in the same range (CDC, 2009; Becker et al., 2003). Values reported similar to those in other Spanish studies</p>
<p>N: Amalgam; NA</p>	<p>Exposure: Metallic Profile of Whole Blood and Plasma</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>Blood Pb decreased by half (12.5 versus 26.3 mg/L, p<0.0001). Differences observed between males and females for Cu and Zn; Cd and Pb higher in smokers. Median plasmatic Hg, did not significantly increase (0.38 versus 0.28 mg/L, P 5 0.11)</p>
<p>Y: Resin filling; NA</p>	<p>Exposure: Urinary BPA</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>Urinary BPA concentrations higher in children with 11 or more surfaces restored with sealants and resin composites versus zero restored surfaces. No difference in group with 1–10 surfaces. After adjusting for gender/age, urinary BPA concentration in children with 11 or more resin composite surfaces: 2.67 lg/g creatinine, higher than those with no filling surfaces (p<0.01)</p>
<p>N: Amalgam; NA</p>	<p>Multiple health/Exposure: FLEHS 1: Venal/cord Hg. FLEHS 2: Hair Hg. HI markers: health and pregnancy, allergy and asthma, fertility and menstruation. (1) genotoxicity markers, (2) endocrine markers: thyroid hormones (TSH, fT3, fT4) and sex hormones (testosterone, oestradiol, SHBG, LH, FSH), gene expression, ct values</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>Hg concentrations in Flemish population low vs other studies and related to participant age and consumption of fish. Significant negative associations between hair Hg and asthma, having received breast feeding as newborn, age at menarche in girls, allergy for animals and free testosterone levels. Significant correlations between hair Hg and genes JAK2, ARID4A, Hist1HA4L (boys) and HLAdrb5, PIAS2, MANN1B1, GIT and ABCA1 (girls). No correlations between Hg-T or MMHg in hair and dental fillings, use of hair coloring products or use of hair care products (e.g. gel, conditioner, makeup)</p>

Y: Amalgam; NA	Immune function: Exposure: Systemic lupus erythematosus disease activity, blood/U-Hg	NR	Pearson's correlation identified a significant negative correlation between hair Hg and BILAG ($r = -0.323$, $p = 0.029$) and SLICC/ACR ($r = -0.377$, $p = 0.038$). Multiple regression analysis identified hair Hg as a significant predictor of disease associated damage as determined by SLICC/ACR ($\beta = -1.769$, 95% confidence interval (CI): -0.155 , 0.019). U-Hg was not related to disease activity or damage. Fish consumption is the primary route of MeHg exposure in humans and the inverse association of hair Hg with disease activity observed here might be explained by the anti-inflammatory effects of n-3 long chain polyunsaturated fatty acids also found in fish
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood Hg and Se concentrations		Identified 30 potential predictors of Hg and 24 of Se, Multivariable model of 14 predictors explained 22.4% of Hg variance (95% CI: 13.0 to 37.1), including 6.9% from blood Se and 3.2% from white fish consumption. 11 predictors explained 15.3% of Se variance (CI: 8.9 to 25.9), including 6.4% from blood Hg, 1.3% from blood lead, and 1.3% from oily fish. Measured genetic variation explained 30% of Hg variance (CI: 8.4 to 51.5) and 37.5% of Se (CI: 10.4 to 64.5). High proportion of Hg and Se variance explained from dietary, sociodemographic, metabolic, and genetic factors. Seafood consumption less predictive of Hg than expected and other factors should be considered when determining exposure
Y: Amalgam; Composite resin	Immune function: Peripheral blood lymphocytes	NR	No significant difference between amalgam vs composite fillings. Association between dental fillings and DNA damage increased by no. fillings and exposure time
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hair Hg, age, gender, body weight and height, frequency fish consumption and no., surface and area DA fillings. Potential factors such as age, gender, body weight, height, BMI	NR	3 groups study participants: ANF (amalgam, no fish); NAF (no amalgam but with fish) and AAF (amalgam and fish). Significant differences THg found in 3 groups ($p = 0.05$). Weak but significant correlation of hair THg with respect to gender and age, but almost no association found between THg and dental fillings. Strong correlation between THg and fish consumption regardless of group. Hair Hg exceeded levels corresponding to EPA reference dose of $0.1 \mu\text{g Hg/kg body weight per day}$ ($1 \mu\text{g Hg/g hair}$) in 6% of population (4% men and 2% women). However, THg limits in subjects not exceeded according to WHO guidelines (benchmark $0.23 \mu\text{g Hg/kg bw/day}$ ($14 \mu\text{g Hg/g maternal hair}$))
Y: Pulverized amalgam, iridium, indium, platinum, menthol and sorbic acid; NA	Allergy: Allergic reaction	Average duration of lesions prior to testing: 32 months (ranging 4–72 months)	15 (60 %) sensitized to 1 or more allergens, total 31 positive reactions. Greatest frequency positive reactions was to dental metals, total 27 positive reactions. Frequency positive reactions: Hg (6/25/24 %), amalgam (6/25/24 %), Ni (4/25/16 %), palladium (4/25/16 %), Co (3/25/12 %), gold (2/25/8 %), chrome (1/25/4 %), indium (1/25/4 %). Clinical relevance of results re: material's presence in mouth seen in 11 (44 %) patients. In 9 patients, replacement of positively tested materials led to healing or to significant regression of mucosal changes

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood Hg, Pb, Cd	Population immigrated to Canada in last 1-5yrs	Higher blood Hg associated with seafood consumption, DAs and traditional remedies; blood Pb with home renovations, sucking on metal jewelry, and cosmetics. Blood Pb and Cd concentrations inversely associated with dairy consumption
Y: Amalgam; NA	Multiple health: MS symptoms, disability, type of immunomodulatory treatment, treatment duration) and dental pathology (dental caries, periodontitis, amalgam dental fillings, gingival bleedings)	NR	Disability status significantly correlated to no. relapses during last year of disease and total no. relapses. Immunomodulatory treatment significantly reduces no. relapses in first year treatment, then disease stabilizes. Disability level highly dependent on no. relapses that occurred in most recent time period. %age of 67.9% of patients reported gingival bleeding. However, bleeding was significantly associated with no. relapses from last year, degree of disability (EDSS) or type of immunomodulatory treatment. Only significant difference: between EDSS scores and presence/absence of DA fillings but sample too small to interpret result
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hair/nail Hg	NA-yearly samples	Male staff higher Hg concentrations than female staff and dentists higher concentrations than other staff. Staff working in dental practices more than fiveyrs old had small but discernable increases in head hair Hg concentration. Use of reusable capsules e.g. Dentomats associated with slight but SS increase in head hair Hg concentrations vs encapsulated amalgam systems. Staff wearing open-toed footwear significantly higher toenail Hg concentrations vs shoe wearers

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hg hair	5yrs following baseline	Mean H-Hg levels: between 0.3 and 0.4 µg/g over 5yrs. 17–29% children had H-Hg levels ≥0.5µg/g, and 5.0 to 8.5% of children levels ≥1µg/g, in any given study year. In adjusted models, fish consumption frequency most robust predictor of high H-Hg. U-Hg mean levels were between 0.7 to 0.9 µg/g creatinine over 2yrs. %age of those with U-Hg≥2.3µg/g creatinine ranged from 4 to 6%. No. amalgam restorations had significant dose-response relationship with U-Hg level. Daily gum chewing in presence of amalgam associated with high U-Hg
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hg Urine	NR	U-Hg levels significantly higher in participants with amalgam surfaces, with average difference of 0.55 µg/g-creatinine. Per amalgam surface, estimated expected increase of 0.04 µg/ g-creatinine. Measured U-Hg levels significantly higher in participants with DA surfaces following oral administration of 2,3-dimercaptopropane-l-sulfonate and meso-2,3-dimercaptosuccinic acid used to mobilize Hg from blood and tissues
Y: Amalgam ; NA	Neuropsych/Exposure: U-Hg concentration; visual memory, manual dexterity	NA	Geometric mean U-Hg levels in DD and DA were 2.52 (2.22) µg/L and 1.98 (1.98) µg/L, respectively. Corresponding indices of chronic occupational Hg ^o exposure, weighted for historical exposure: 1212 (1877) and 316 (429). 5-HTTLPR status was 40% and 20% wild type, 40% and 56% single allelic substitution, and 20% and 24% double allelic substitution for the two genders. DD and DA were evaluated separately. Regression analyses controlled for age, premorbid intelligence, frequency of alcohol per week, and education. 5-HTTLPR polymorphism associated with 5 behavioral measures in DD and with 12 behavioral measures in DA. Mood scores more consistently associated with variant in both groups. Strongest evidence for additive effect for U-Hg and 5-HTTLPR polymorphism in both groups for tests of Finger Tap Alternate and Hand Steadiness Factor
Y: Amalgam; CD/non CD	Exposure: Urinary and blood Hg (Hg) levels in celiac patients and healthy controls.	NA	Hg blood/urinary levels: 2.4 ± 2.3/1.0 ± 1.4, 10.2 ± 6.7/2.2 ± 3.0 and 3.7±2.7/1.3±1.2 in untreated CD, treated CD, and healthy controls, respectively. Hg levels significantly higher in celiac patients following gluten-free diet. No differences found regarding fish intake and no. amalgam fillings. No demographic or clinical data significantly associated with Hg levels in biologic samples

Y Borderline: Amalgam; NA	Multiple health/Exposure: Toenail Hg, infant infections, allergies and/or respiratory symptoms	Infant: 4, 8 and 12 months. Maternal toenail Hg at ~28-30wk gestation	Among women who ate fish during pregnancy, higher maternal toenail Hg concentrations associated with increased risk of lower respiratory infections and respiratory symptoms requiring a doctor visit among infants age 9–12 months RR 1.4 (95% CI: 1.1, 1.9) and 1.2 (95% CI: 1.0, 1.4) respectively). Reduced risk of lower respiratory infections among infants 0–4 months of age (RR=0.7 (95% CI: 0.5, 1.0). Little to no evidence of associations of toenail Hg with upper respiratory infections, allergy or eczema at any age to 1yr. Among infants of mothers who did not consume fish, elevated risk of upper respiratory infections requiring doctor visit in relation to having DAs during pregnancy (RR=1.5 (95% CI: 1.1, 2.1))
N: Amalgam; na	Exposure: Urinary Cd, cotinine, phthalate metabolites, hair Hg	NR	Hair Hg increased significantly with consumption of fish/ seafood and no.amalgam tooth fillings (in children). Positive association with family educational level. No influence of age observed. Urinary Cd and hair Hg levels lower than health-based guidelines with one exception

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Trace elements in blood, plasma and erythrocytes: Mn, Co, Cu, Zn, Se and Mo, Li, Be, V, Cr, Ni, Ga, As, Rb, Sr, Ag, Cd, Sn, Cs, Au, Hg, Tl, Pb and U	NR	Higher blood and plasma Cu, and erythrocyte Mn levels in women found. In men, blood Zn, plasma Zn, Mn and Se, and erythrocyte Cu levels higher. Zn levels higher in 30–39yrs age group. Pb and Sr increased with age. Smoking positively affected Cd, Pb, Cs and Rb; seafood consumption increased As, Hg and Zn; and amalgam increased Hg, Ag and Cu levels
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Maternal U-Hg, Infant and umbilical cord Hg	Umbilical cord: delivery	Predictors of cord blood Hg included maternal fish consumption and foreign birth of mother. Predictors of U-Hg included foreign birth of the mother, no.DAs, and special product use. No reports of Hg use in ritualistic practices or cosmetics; some women reported using religious medals/charms
Y: Amalgam; NA	MSK: Arthritis	NR	Arthritis rate significantly increased in exposed group vs unexposed group in unadjusted (7.68-fold) and adjusted (4.89-fold) models. Arthritis (per 10000 weighted-person-years) was 6.0-fold significantly increased in exposed group (6.2) vs unexposed group (1.06). Significant bimodal dose-dependent relationship between DAFS and arthritis rate observed. Arthritis rate increased with increasing DAFS (peak among persons with 4-7 DAFS) and, subsequently, decreased among those with >6 DAFS. Sgnificant decrease arthritis rate among persons with >13 DAFS vs persons with 4 to 7 DAFS. Significant association between DAFS and arthritis risk and dose-dependent DAFS associated immune-stimulation/immune-suppression with arthritis risk observed

Y: Amalgam; NA	Respiratory: Asthma	NR	Significantly increased incidence rate reported asthma in exposed group vs unexposed group in unadjusted (4.46-fold) and adjusted (4.84-fold) models. Dose-response relationship observed for risk of reported asthma/DAFS in unadjusted (1.073) and adjusted (1.076) models. Frequency reported asthma (per 10,000 weighted-personyrs) 3.66-fold significantly increased in exposed group (2.06) vs unexposed group (0.56)
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: U-Hg, daily estimated mg of Hg vapour/kg bodyweight	NR	Median daily U-Hg excretion ~2.5-fold higher among pregnant women with amalgams vs pregnant women without amalgams. Significant correlation between no.amalgam surfaces and daily U-Hg excretion. Among pregnant women with amalgams, estimated median daily Hg vapor dose from amalgams: 7.66 µg of Hg and 0.073 µg of Hg/Kg bodyweight. Among all pregnant women, ~28% received daily Hg vapor doses from amalgams above least restrictive US EPA safety limit and ~36% received above most restrictive California EPA safety limit
Y: Amalgam vs NA	Autism/ASD diagnosis	NA	Logistic regression analysis (age, gender, race, and region of residency adjusted) by quintile of maternal dental amalgams during pregnancy revealed the ratio of autism:ASD (severe:mild) were about 1 (no effect) for ≤5 amalgams and increased for ≥6 amalgams. Subjects with ≥6 amalgams were 3.2-fold significantly more likely to be diagnosed with autism (severe), in comparison to ASD (mild), than subjects with ≤5 amalgams
Y: Amalgam; No amalgam filling	Exposure: U-Hg	NA	About 91 million (57.8%) adults had ≥1 amalgam surface and about 67 million (42.2%) had no amalgams. A β-coefficient=0.041 significantly correlated the no. amalgam surfaces to daily amounts of U-Hg. Differences were observed for gender and racial groups. Daily Hg vapor doses from amalgams were in excess of the most restrictive California's EPA safety limit for about 86 million (54.3%) adults and in excess of the least restrictive US EPA safety limit among about 16 million (10.4%) adults. The mean allowable no. amalgam surfaces ranged from 1.28 for adult females under the California's EPA safety limit to 16.23 for adult males under the US EPA safety limit

Y: Amalgam; Composite resin	Exposure: U-Hg	7xannual reviews after dental treatment	SS dose-dependent correlation between cumulative exposure to Hg from DAs and U-Hg levels, after covariate adjustment. U-Hg levels increased by 18% to 52% among 8 to 18 year old individuals, respectively, with average exposure to amalgams, vs subjects with no exposure to amalgams
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood (total Hg, Cd, and lead) and hair (total Hg)	Baseline wk 6-8 (amalgam count). Follow up wk 32 pregnancy hair sample taken	Median values total Hg (B-Hg 0.70 µg/L; range 0.27–2.1 µg/L), Cd (0.30 µg/L, 0.05–4.8 µg/L) and Pb (11.0 µg/L, 4.2–79 µg/L) in whole blood low in total material, as were hair Hg concentrations (Hair-Hg 0.22 µg/g, 0.04–0.83 µg/g). In a multiple linear regression model, B-Hg related to the no.fish meals/wk and no. occlusal amalgam fillings (multiple r = 0.51; p<.001). Whole blood levels Hg, Cd, and Pb lower than suggested biological reference intervals, and did not indicate risks for adverse health effects
N: Amalgam; NA	Health Other/Exposure: Association of electromagnetic sensitivity and heavy metal exposure. Venous blood: Hg, Pb, Cd	NR	Heavy metal load is of no concern in most cases of EHS but might play role in exceptional cases. No significant differences blood Hg levels between patients and controls (p=0.352). Only EHS subjects showed Hg blood levels above HBM values. Two patients (1.5%) had levels above 5 µg/L and one patient even exceeded 15 µg/L (241 µg/L). In subgroup analysis EHS subjects without amalgam displayed higher Hg levels than controls without fillings, however difference not significant after correction for multiple testing. Weak correlation between Hg levels and age (r= 0.17, p=0.05 for EHS patients and r= 0.217, p=0.029 in controls)]
Borderline: Amalgam; NA	Autism/Exposure: Prenatal blood HG, autism	2yr post pregnancy (restorations given during pregnancy assessed)	No suggestion of an adverse effect of total prenatal blood Hg levels on diagnosed autism (AOR 0.89; 95% CI 0.65, 1.22) per SD of Hg (p=0.485). Only indication of adverse effects concerned a measure of poor social cognition when mother ate no fish, where AOR was 1.63 [95% CI 1.02, 2.62] per SD of Hg (p=0.041), significantly different from association among the offspring of fish-eaters (AOR=0.74 [95% CI 0.41, 1.35])

Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood Hg	2 year post pregnancy (restorations given during pregnancy assessed)	Contribution to variance of mothers' TBHg levels by dental variables: 6.47%, comparable to 8.75% for seafood consumption in this population. Dietary and dental variables explained 20.16% of variance, with socio-demographic variables contributing a further 3.40%. No. amalgams at start of pregnancy accounted for most of variance in dental variables...In regard to dental features, poor sociability appeared to show significant relationships, but increased maternal exposure to DA associated with lower rates of extreme levels of autistic traits. Upon adjustment, four significant associations at 10% level; all indicated protective effect associated with exposures that would have increased mothers' Hg level
Y: Amalgam; NA	Genotoxicity/Exposure: Urinary/hair Hg, DNA	NR	Hair Hg (geometric mean (95% C1): 0.37 (0.31–0.44) µg/g) and U-Hg (0.70 (0.60–0.83) µg/L) associated with sources of exposure (fish consumption and DAs, respectively). Multivariable linear regression: trend of SEPP1 hypomethylation with increasing hair Hg levels significant among males (p<0.05), remaining when excluding non-dentists
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hg levels in biomarkers of elemental Hg (urine) and methylHg (hair and blood)	NR	Hg levels in biomarkers of elemental Hg (urine) and methylHg (hair and blood) higher than general US population. Geometric means (95% C1): 1.28 (1.19–1.37) µg/l in urine, 0.60 (0.54–0.67) µg/g in hair and 3.67 (3.38–3.98) µg/l in blood. Multivariable linear regression: amalgams predicted U-Hg levels along with total yrs in dentistry, amalgams handled, working hours and sex
Y: Amalgam; NA	CVD/Exposure: Hg levels in hair and urine samples analyzed as biomarkers of methylHg and elemental Hg exposure. Blood pressure (systolic, diastolic), pulse	NR	Distribution of Hg in hair (mean, range: 0.45, 0.02–5.18 µg/g) and urine (0.94, 0.03–5.54 µg/L) correspond well with the US National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. Linear regression models: significant associations between DBP (adjusted for blood pressure medication use) and hair Hg (n=262, p=0.02). Elemental Hg exposure associated with significant SBP decrease (n=262, p=0.04) driven by male population. Associations between blood pressure and two forms of Hg found at exposure levels relevant to general population, and associations varied according to type of Hg exposure and gender
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hg urine/hair levels, DNA	NR	Average urine (1.06± 1.24 ug/L) and hair Hg levels (0.49± 0.63 ug/g) similar to national U.S. population averages. Taqman assays used to genotype DNA from buccal swab samples at 15 polymorphic sites in genes implicated in Hg metabolism. Linear regression modeling assessed the ability of polymorphisms to modify relationship between Hg biomarker levels and exposure sources (e.g., amalgams, fish consumption). Five polymorphisms were significantly associated with U-Hg levels (GSTT1 deletion), hair Hg levels (GSTP1-105, GSTP1-114, GSS 5'), or both (SEPP1 3'UTR). Polymorphisms in selenoproteins and glutathione-related genes may influence elimination of Hg in urine and hair or Hg retention following exposures to elemental Hg (via DAs) and methylHg (via fish consumption)

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Biological markers of exposure: concentrations of main toxic metals Pb, Cd and Hg in maternal blood and three types of breast milk throughout lactation stages. Biological markers of effects were the levels of essential elements Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn and Se in maternal serum and breast milk	Breast milk: up to day 4 (colostrum), between day 5 and 10 (transitional milk), between day 20-30 after parturition (mature milk sample)	No.DA fillings correlated with total Hg concentrations in colostrum (=0.489; p=0.005) and transitional milk (=0.309; p=0.018)
Y-borderline: Amalgam; NA	Pregnancy outcomes/Exposure: Pb and Hg concentrations were measured in maternal blood and hair, placenta, cord, blood, meconium, and breast milk, infant anthropometry	Postpartum week 2-8	Median Pb and total Hg contents low, i.e., 25 µg/L (maternal blood-Pb), 13 µg/L (cord blood-Pb), 0.7 µg/L (maternal blood-Hg), and 1.1 µg/L (cord blood-Hg). Hg levels in maternal and fetal tissues frequently correlated (rN0.3, Pb0.05, respectively). Pb: only maternal blood and cord blood concentrations correlated (p=0.043). Cord blood levels indicated higher Hg exposure but lower Pb exposure relative to maternal blood contents. Adjusted CATREG models indicated significant predictors of birth length (placenta-Pb, gestational length, meconium-Pb), birth weight (placenta-Pb, gestational length, maternal blood Pb), and head circumference (maternal education, maternal height). Besides one significant correlation between maternal hair Hg and birth length, Hg levels not associated with newborn anthropometry
Y: Amalgam; NA	Immune function/Exposure: Serum antibody (IgG) levels, Hg in saliva, allergic sensitization to metals (n=4 patients). occurrence specific antibodies to antglomerular basement membrane in individuals with DAs	Patients: median duration of exposure to Hg vapor from dental amalgams 27.5yrs (range 8–40). dentists had been occupationally exposed to high concentrations (up to 1 mg/m ³) of Hg vapor for 10yrs, whereas the dental assistant had been exposed to background Hg levels of 0.1–0.2 mg/m ³ for twoyrs	No patients showed evidence of anti-GBM autoimmunity, either in subgroups with strong allergy to Hg or its compounds (i.e., organic Hg) or in patients who had past thimerosal-containing vaccines coverage (7 of 24). No evidence of circulating anti-GBM antibodies in subjects suffering from adverse events due to long term exposure to Hg from DAs, even in individuals with allergy to Hg

<p>Y: A) Amalgam (removal of fillings); B) Amalgam removal and non-specific detoxification C) health promotion program without removal</p>	<p>Exposure: Blood/U-Hg</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>After amalgam removal, inorganic Hg reduced in plasma and red cells, stabilizing at 27% of preremoval levels after 60 days. Concentrations organic Hg in plasma remained unchanged, indicating no change in dietary uptake of organic Hg. Concentration of organic Hg in red cells of group A was in the early postremoval phase lower and in the late postremoval phase higher than preremoval control (p=0.01 for low-high difference). A increase in organic Hg found in red cells of group B after 60 days. Thus, effect of removal on organic Hg levels in combined group A+B compared with values of group C in a linear mixed effects (LME) model which showed a significant increase with time in group A+B (p = 0.028). In all groups, time profiles of urinary concentration and excretion of total-Hg were very similar to those of inorganic-Hg levels in plasma. From extrapolations of blood and urine data it was estimated that the amalgam-related inhalation and ingestion of Hg species were within the limits proposed by WHO, ATSDR and EPA. The integrated daily Hg dose absorbed from amalgam was estimated up to 3mg for an</p>
<p>N: Amalgam; NA</p>	<p>Autism/Exposure: Postdiagnosis blood Hg concentrations in preschool-age children with/without autism, adjusting for recent exposures through diet, personal care products, vaccines, and DAs</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>Fish consumption strongly predicted total Hg concentration. AU/ASD children ate less fish. After adjustment for fish and other Hg sources, blood Hg levels in AU/ASD children similar to TD children (p=0.75); also among non-fish eaters (p=0.73). Direct effect of AU/ASD diagnosis on blood Hg not through indirect pathway of altered fish consumption was 12% reduction. TD children had lower blood Hg concentrations in all analyses. DAs in children with gum-chewing or teeth-grinding habits predicted higher levels</p>
<p>Y: Amalgam; NA</p>	<p>Multiple health/Exposure: U-Hg, Hg exposure symptoms, neurobehavioural tests, DNA genetic testings, mood tests, medical conditions</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>No consistent associations between either U-Hg concentration or chronic index of Hg exposure and any symptom category. Significant/consistent associations between increased symptoms and 5-HTTLPR polymorphism involving two copies of short or “s” allele (full mutation), but not with polymorphism involving only one copy (heterozygous), demonstrating gene-dose relationship for symptom reporting. These findings suggest within this population increased symptoms depression, anxiety, and memory associated with 5-HTTLPR polymorphism among males and females</p>
<p>Y: Amalgam; NA</p>	<p>Multiple health/Exposure: U-Hg, Hg exposure symptoms, neurobehavioural tests, DNA genetic testings, mood tests, medical conditions</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>No consistent patterns of association between either U-Hg concentration or chronic index of Hg exposure and any symptom category observed. Consistent significant significant associations between increased symptoms and COMT polymorphism involving double allelic substitution (full mutation) compared to subjects with no substitutions. Associations with mood limited to polymorphism status among female dental assistants, and observed for 4/6 mood factors and overall mood score</p>

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood Cd, Pb, Hg	NR	Hg “hot spot” areas in China had B-Hg 3.1 (95% CI: 2.7–3.5) times higher, and Ecuador 1.5 (95% CI: 1.2–1.9) times higher, vs urban areas (urban GM: 2.45 µg/l and 3.23 µg/l, respectively). Besides industrial exposure, traffic correlated with B-Cd; male sex, environmental tobacco smoke, and offal consumption with B-Pb; and fish consumption and amalgam fillings with B-Hg. Correlations could only marginally explain regional differences
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood Cd, Pb, Hg	NR	European cities showed only minor differences for B-Cd (geometric means 0.11–0.17 µg/L) and B-Pb (14–20 µg/L), but larger for B-Hg (0.12–0.94 µg/L). Means non-European countries: 0.21–0.26, 32–71, and 0.3–3.2 µg/L, respectively. For Blood-Cd in European samples, traffic intensity close to home was SS determinant, for Blood-Hg fish consumption and amalgam fillings, and for B-Pb sex (boys higher). European city children's Blood-Cd and Blood-Pb vary slightly between countries; Blood-Hg differs considerably, due to varying tooth restoration practices and fish intake
Y: Methacrylates; Dental assistants exposed to methacrylates compared to those unexposed	Respiratory: Prolonged/repeated occurrence of respiratory symptoms (nasal symptoms, hoarseness, cough or phlegm production, dyspnoea, wheezing in connection with dyspnoea) during past year at times other than in connection with cold; occurrence of asthma/chronic bronchitis	4 categories duration of daily(meth)acrylate exposure: 1) no exposure; 2) up to 5yrs; 3) >5–10yrs; (iv) >10 year	Daily use of methacrylates significantly increased risk adult-onset asthma (adjusted OR 2.65, 95% CI 1.14–7.24), nasal symptoms(1.37, 1.02–1.84), and work-related cough or phlegm (1.69, 1.08–2.71). Nasal symptoms dose–response relation with increasing yrs of exposure to methacrylates, and those with >10yrs of exposure increased risk of hoarseness, dyspnoea+ wheezing with dyspnoea. Dental assistants with atopic disease history susceptible to methacrylates exposure, adjusted OR for adult asthma: 4.18 (95% CI 1.02–28.55) and nasal symptoms 2.11 (1.08–4.19)
N: Amalgam; NA	Renal/Exposure: U-Hg, kidney biomarkers	Plant workers: exposed min.1yr. General population: living in study area min.1yr	In general population, median U-HgC higher in Italian (1.2mg/g C) than Polish (0.22 mg/g C) or Swedish (0.21 mg/g C) subjects, and no effect of living close to CA plants shown. DA, chewing on amalgam, and fish consumption positively associated with U-HgC
N: Amalgam ; NA	Exposure: THg and MeHg in vein and cord blood samples	Amalgam use within 6 months?	THg were 1.02 -11.53 µg/L, 1.48-15.97 µg/L in vein and cord blood respectively. THg cord blood concentration approx 150% vs venous blood. MeHg levels of 36 participants: 2.60±1.11 µg/L in venous blood and 4.70±1.97 µg/L in cord blood. MeHg were 85% and 91% level of THg in vein and cord blood of Korean pregnant women. No relationship between DA treatments and Hg concentration within recent 6 months. Some vaccinated participants high blood/cord-blood Hg concentration (NSS). Hg concentration increasing tendency with increased fish intake

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: U-Hg	NA	Most statistically important co-factors: school location, age and daily fish consumption. No association DA. Daily fish consumption associated with increasing amount of fish consumed in females
N: Multiple!; NA	Allergy: Positive patch test reaction	NA	Oral diseases included oral lichen planus (54.5%), cheilitis (27.3%), burning mouth syndrome (9.1%), and others (9.1%). Thirty-one of 44 patients (70.5%) had positive reactions to one or more allergens. Most commonly detected allergens were gold sodium thiosulfate (25.0%) and Ni sulfate (25.0%), followed by potassium dichromate (22.7%), Co (15.9%), palladium (6.8%), Hg (4.5%), Cu (4.5%), and methylhydroquinone (4.5%). 6/24 patients with oral lichen planus had symptom in areas adjacent to dental materials and positive patch test reactions to allergens contained in the suspected dental materials
Y: Amalgam and composite resin; NA	Oral health: Mucosal lesions	11yrs	Surfaces with composite resin restorations associated with slightly higher risk of mucosal lesions vs without restorations (OR 1.04; 95% CI: 1.01-1.07). No significant association between amalgam restorations and mucosal lesions
Y: Composite; NA	Exposure: Salivary/urinary concentrations BPA/other	Investigated effects of composite placement for three postplacement periods: within 1 hr, 1-8hrs, 9-30hrs	BPA salivary concentrations+some related compounds increased immediately (within 1hr) after composite placement. Salivary BPA concentrations+most study compounds returned to preresoration levels within 8hrs after placement. With exception 43% increase in BPA, concentrations of study compounds in urine returned to preresoration levels 9-30hrs after restoration placement. Concentrations in saliva lower when rubber dam used; rubber dam no effect on urinary concentrations of the measured compounds. Similar changes in- study compound levels in both saliva and urine between participants who received anterior or posterior restorations
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Meconium samples	NA	Correlation Hg concentration in meconium with sociodemographic characteristics of studied group e.g. living residence place, dietary habits and influence of amalgam fillings. The highest concentrations Hg observed in mothers who consumed fish, particularly in coastal living area. Slightly higher concentrations of Hg in samples in urban living area vs rural residence, potentially because of strong effect of disposed Hg from industrial plants into Split and Dalmatian County during last 50yrs

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood/urinary/hair Hg	Mothers: blood taken first and last trimesters	Actual exposure to Hg indicated by levels of Hg in children's blood (geometric mean (GM) 0.92 mg/L), mother's blood (GM1.86 mg/L), children's urine (GM 1.08 mg/g crea.), mother's urine (GM 2.51 mg/L), children's hair (GM 241 ng/g) and mother's hair (GM 251 ng/g) higher in two study groups from Idrija vs control groups from rural areas, but still at level of a "normal" population and reflects exposure to elemental Hg (Hg ⁰) from DA and, atmospheric Hg ⁰ . Internal doses Hg during pregnancy did not decrease bioavailability of Se
Y: Amalgam; NA	Health other: Health complaints according to Giessen Subjective Complaints List (GGB-24): 24 different health complaints; self-reported health changes after amalgam removal; factors perceived as related to amalgam removal	Time since removal: <1 yr, 1-4yrs, 5-9yrs, 10 or more yrs	324 participants included in study. Majority of participants reported improved health after amalgam removal, even though mean degree complaints severity still high. Exhaustion and MSK complaints most severe, reflecting 38% of participants reported poor to very poor current health. Associations found between amalgam removal, and improved health, no precautions applied, and time since removal
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hair Hg	NA	Highest total Hg content: 3.55 µg/g, lowest content: 0.015 µg/g. No correlation was found between the Hg levels in the sampled hair and the subject's age, gender, and the amount of amalgam fillings
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hair Hg	NA	No correlation between hair-Hg and age, gender or amalgam fillings. Correlation between fish consumption and amount of Hg found in hair samples
Y: Resin composite; NA	Exposure: Salivary BPA	7 days after filling	Before new composite resin filling, no significant difference between with/without existing filling of composite resin and BPA level in saliva not correlated to no. filled surfaces with composite resin. However, BPA level in saliva increased to average 3.64 mg/L from average 0.15 mg/L after filling 5 min. BPA level increased in proportion with number filled surfaces. BPA level decreased to average 0.59 after filling 7d. However > BPA level before new composite resin filling

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Concentrations toxic metals Pb, Cd, Hg in maternal blood and three types of breast milk throughout lactation stages. Biological markers: levels of essential elements Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn and Se in maternal serum and breast milk	Blood: collected morning after parturition. Milk samples during visit after delivery: up to day 4, between day 5 and 10 (transitional milk) and between day 20 and 30d after parturition (maturemilk sample)	no.DA fillings correlated with total Hg concentrations in colostrum (=0.489; p=0.005) and transitional milk (=0.309; p=0.018)
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: U-Hg and As, blood Pb and cadium	NA	No consistent difference in mean internal load of metals between four investigation areas. Factors influencing concentrations: fish consumption last 48h, which impacted As (factor 2), and amalgam fillings, which accounted for increase in Hg (factor 4.6). In 2002/03 study period, levels above limit of health concern for children (German HBM values) found in approx. 0.5% of Pb measurements (maximum value 180 mg/l blood) and in about 0.2% of the Hg measurements (maximum value 8.2 mg/l urine)

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: U-Hg, Blood lead, chlororganics DDE, HCB, PCB-138, PCB 153 and PCB-180	NA	Median U-Hg concentrations decreased from 0.25 g/l to a value below limit of quantification of 0.2 g/l; the 95th %ile reduced from 3.1g/l to < 0.2 g/l. Decline of amalgam fillings in children during investigation period strongly influenced internal Hg concentrations
N (deprioritise): Different dental materials contained in restorations; NA	Allergy/Oral health: Association hypersensitivity reactions to metals (patch test reactions) and OLP (oral lichenoid planus)	NA	Patch tests performed 24 patients with histopathologic and/or clinical diagnosis of OLP. Of these, 16 (67%) positive patch-test readings. Min.8 (50%) of these patients had clinically relevant reactions. 10/16 patients (63%) had reactions to metals. In most of these patients, troublesome areas tended to localize adjacent to metallic dental restorations. Of nine patients (56%) who had reactions to fragrances, flavorings, gallates, and/or diallyl disulfide, majority improved after avoiding these allergens
Y: Amalgam; No amalgam	Oral health: Association oral mucosa lesions and DA	NA	Most frequent location for both groups was buccal mucosa and bilateral presentation. No clinical or histopathological SS differences found between OLP with/without DA
Y: Resin composites; Non exposure to BPA materials/resin composites	Exposure: Urinary BPA	NA	Significantly higher urinary BPA level in group of dental patients vs dental students (Sig.p=0.001). No significant differences in BPA urinary levels concerning gender characteristics (Sig.p=0.476).. significantly higher mean rank of BPA for control group of dental patients, vs dental students (Z=-3.816, p=0.000). Urinary BPA confirm the ubiquitous general population exposure to Bis A, but no higher than health-based guidance values of BPA urinary level. Significantly higher urinary BPA level and mean rank BPA in dental patients vs one of dental students, with no significant differences concerning the gender characteristics
Y: Resin composites; Glass ionomers, resin dentures, root canal filling materials/chemical agents	Allergy: Skin patch-tested with methacrylic monomers and glutaraldehyde	NA	Among dental students, highest frequency concomitant sensitization was TEGDMA and G (15.5%). In patients highest frequency of concomitant sensitization was EGDMA and G (16.4%). Frequency of concomitant sensitization among dental professionals much lower, highest rate to TEGDMA and G (7.7%). Students from dental technician school, where exposure to glutaraldehyde less likely, lesser risk concomitant sensitization

Y: Resin composites; Glass ionomers, resin dentures, root canal filling materials/chemical agents	Allergy: Skin patch testing for sensitisation found in dental materials e.g. Methylmethacrylate (2-HEMA, Bis-GMA), formaldehyde	NA	From the allergic to formaldehyde students of 3rd and 4th year of dental medicine, 46.2% also sensitized to MMA. Among patients, incidence of cross-sensitization to formaldehyde and methacrylic monomers: TEGDMA – 20.6%, ethyleneglycol dimethacrylate – 20.7%, 2-HEMA – 20.7% tetrahydrofurfuryl methacrylate – 24.1%. Contact allergy to MMA diagnosed among 22.7%, and TEGDMA – among 27.1% of students 3rd and 4th year of dental medicine. Occupationally unexposed dental patients: prevalence of contact allergy to ethyleneglycol dimethacrylate 20.7%, Bis-GMA – 27.6%, 2-HEMA – 44.9% tetrahydrofurfuryl methacrylate – 38.0%
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Total blood Hg	NA	Survey participants with no dental amalgams significantly lower mean blood THg levels vs participants with 11-25 amalgams vs 26 or more amalgams. Difference remained SS (p=0.0077 for 11-25 amalgams, p=0.0003 for 26 or more amalgams) when controlling for total fish/shellfish consumption. No difference observed between participants with no amalgams and those with 1-10 amalgams
N (deprioritise): Several metals contained in dental materials and restorations (Ni sulfate, Co II chloride hexahydrate, goldsodium thiosulfate); NA	Oral health: Association hypersensitivity reactions to metals (patch test reactions) and BMS	4yrs of historical data were reviewed?	142 consecutive patients with BMS, 132 patch tested; 89 (67%) had allergic patch test reactions. Of patients with positive results, 66 (74%) had results that were deemed to have possible relevance. Most common allergens: Ni sulfate 2.5%, dodecyl gallate 0.3%, octyl gallate 0.3%, fragrance mix 8%, benzoyl peroxide 1%, and cinnamicalcohol 1%.
Y: Resin-composite: bisphenyl-glycidyl-dimethacrylate bisGMA based; Resin composite: urethane-modified bisGMA based	Exposure: In vivo chemical degradation sustained: Human salivary esterase activity presence of BPA and bisHPPP)	7 days	Overall mean ± standard error (SE) HSDE activity: 23.4 ± 1.9 U/mL, no statistical difference between Z250 (22.6 ± 2.8 U/mL) and TPH (24.1 ± 2.1 U/mL) groups (p=0.69). BPA was not detected from any rinse samples. BisHPPP detected from both composites only in rinse samples immediately after resin composite placement (0.59 µg/mm ² ± 0.16 and 0.68 µg/mm ² ± 0.16 for Z250 and TPH, respectively, p=0.767). No SS correlation between HSDE and bisHPPP in saliva for Z250 group (r=0.071, p=0.723), TPH group (r=0.266, p=0.155), and both groups combined (r=0.080, p=0.549)

Y: Amalgam; composite	Exposure: Urinary Hg	5yrs	At end of follow-up, average (\pm SD) cumulative exposure: 10.3 \pm 6.1 surfaces and 5.7 \pm 2.9 teeth ever filled with amalgam, corresponding to 30 \pm 21 surface-years. Amalgam measures and U-Hg moderately correlated. Of amalgam exposure measures, current total of amalgam surfaces most robust predictor of current U-Hg, posterior occlusal surface-years best for cumulative U-Hg. In multivariate models, each additional amalgam surface present associated with 9% increase in current U-Hg, and each additional posterior occlusal surface-year associated with 3% increase in cumulative U-Hg excretion ($p < 0.001$)
Y: BisGMA based dental composites; NA	Exposure: Urinary BPA	6mnths	Mean change BPA pretreatment and next-day: 1.71 ng/mL (sd=9.94) overall and 0.87 (sd=5.98). Geater number composite surface-restorations associated with higher BPA in next-day sample (posterior occlusal $e\beta=1.47$, 95% CI 1.18–1.83; $P<0.001$), but this attenuated after restricting to 88 participants with ≤ 4 fillings ($e\beta=1.19$, 95% CI 0.86, 1.64), and no association observed using 14-day ($e\beta=0.94$, 95% CI 0.75–1.18) or 6- month ($e\beta=0.88$, 95% CI 0.74–1.04) samples

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood/U-Hg	10yrs	Having silver-colored fillings on five or more teeth associated with highest 95th %ile for U-Hg (4.06 µg/L; 95% CI=3.1, 5.9). Geometric mean U-Hg levels associated with increasing no. fillings in the adjusted model (p<0.001)
Y: Composite ; NA: bisGMA-based sealant	Exposure: U-BPA	16wks post treatment	Overall, uBPA concentrations 86% higher (95% confidence interval [CI] 42% to 143%, p<0.001) at 2d posttreatment vs pretreatment concentrations. uBPA concentrations 2d posttreatment vs pretreatment tended to be higher (112%, 95% CI 53% to 194%) among those receiving treatment on >4 surfaces than those receiving treatment on ≤4 surfaces (50%, 95% CI -2% to 130%). 2d after treatment, uBPA significantly > pretreatment concentrations in children receiving nitrous oxide but not those receiving general anesthesia. Among all findings, uBPA concentrations returned to baseline by 4wk
Y: Resin composites; NA (Resin sealants)	Exposure: Urinary BPA	NA	In adjusted analysis, children with seven to 42 restorations had geometric mean BPA concentrations 20% higher than those of children with no restorations (95% CI, <6% to 53%; p=.13). Neither of these adjusted estimates was SS

Y: Amalgam vs no amalgam	Exposure: total and inorganic Hg in erythrocytes, plasma, urine, and saliva	NR	Concentrations inorganic mercury in blood and of total mercury in urine/saliva differed significantly between individuals with amalgam fillings and amalgam-free volunteers, but not between symptomatic patients and healthy volunteers with amalgam fillings. Urine Hg levels better correlated with blood than saliva data. Levels of organic Hg equal in all groups
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Ni hair	NA	Effect of several factors on Ni content in hair was examined: lifestyle habits (e.g. hair coloring, hair spray, hair straighteners, hair drier, drugs); dietary factors (e.g. yoghurts, blue cheese, lettuce, lemon, mushroom, egg, butter); other (e.g. solarium, cigarette smoking, tap water pipes, tinned food, PVC foil, photocopier, amalgam, filling). Exposure to Ni ions can occur from different sources: lifestyle, eating habits and environmental exposure
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hg hair	NA	Mean Hg level in hair of whole population (n=321) was 0.203±0.181 mg·kg ⁻¹ . Hg in hair of subjects who consumed fish exceeded upper limit of reference value: 0.397 mg·kg ⁻¹ . Subjects who declared consumption of fish, honey, and mouldy cheese/:statistically more Hg: 60.5%, 35.4%, and 37.8%, respectively, than those who did not eat these. No effect from place of residence, presence of pollution emitters, gender, age, weight, height, presence of amalgam fillings, hair dyeing, and smoking cigarettes on hair Hg
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Pb hair	NA	Amalgam filling could be a potential source of lead in hair. Subjects with amalgam filling at present had 17 % higher content of lead in hair than subjects who never had amalgam filling

Y: Resin composite (Before restoration); Resin composite (After restoration)	Exposure: Salivary methacrylate monomers: Bis-GMA, UDMA, TEGDMA, Bis-EMA	7 days	Amounts detected ranged from 0.028 to 9.65 µg/ml ¹ for Bis-GMA, from 0.015 to 0.19 µg/ml ¹ for HEMA, and from 0.004 to 1.2 µg/ml ¹ for UDMA. TEGDMA detected in 4 samples. Bis-EMA not detected. Monomers not detected in saliva samples collected before treatment, or 24h or 7d after treatment, with exception of one sample, 24h after treatment where HEMA detected
Y: Multiple; NA	Allergy: Subjective and objective health complaints (Listed in paper) Patch tested allergy	NR	
Y: Amalgam/Hg exposure; No Hg exposure	Multiple health: Psychosomatic symptoms, mood, memory, concentration, fatigue, sleep disturbance, anxiety, perception health status and life, MSK symptoms	NA	Dental assistants reported significant higher occurrence of neurological symptoms; psychosomatic symptoms, problems with memory, concentration, fatigue and sleep disturbance, but not for mood. This was found by analyses of variance, adjusting for age, education, alcohol consumption, smoking and personality traits. For each specific neurological symptom, adjusted logistic regression analyses were performed, showing that these symptoms were mainly from arms, hands, legs and balance organs
N: Amalgam; No amalgam fillings	Allergy/Exposure: Hair/U-Hg, patch test for allergy	NA	For male Hg-PT(+) group, Hg-u and Hg-h were higher than male reference Hg-PT(-) group; Early morning Hg-u values and after supper significantly different. Multiple regression analysis: increases in level of fish intake, mercuriochrome usage, and NA independently increased Hg-u measured in early morning for both gender groups. NA significantly affected Hg-u

Y: Amalgam; NA	Immune function/Exposure: Cord blood Hg, maternal toenail Hg, immune cell phenotyping in cord blood PBMC, t-cell population cord blood	Late pregnancy/delivery	Frequency NKT and activated naïve Th cells positively associated with prenatal toenail Hg concentrations and no. maternal silver-Hg DAs, respectively. Placental gene expression analyses: distinct gene signatures associated with Hg exposure. Decreased placental expression of histone demethylase, KDM4DL, associated with both higher prenatal and postpartum maternal toenail Hg levels among male infants+remained SS adjusting for fish/seafood consumption. Gestational exposure to Hg concentrations contribute to alterations in both T cells and gene expression in placenta at birth, which may inform mechanisms of Hg immunotoxicity
Y: Composite resins; NA: irrelevant materials included e.g. acrylic materials entering structures of dental prostheses	Oral health: Pulpal/gingival inflammation, burning mouth syndrome, allergies, mucosal inflammation and ulceration	NA	Stomatitis and manifestations caused by conventional prostheses followed by inflammations of dental pulp caused by treatment of dental cavities with composite resins most frequently reported
Y: Amalgam fillings, dental crowns, prostheses, orthodontic retention wires; NA	Allergy/Oral health: Ni and palladium sensitization (positive patch test); association between exposure to dental alloys and oral symptoms/complaints (eczema, OLLs, stomatitis)	NA	906 patients included, 24.3% reacted to palladium, 25.2% to Ni. Monosensitization rate: 6–7% for both metals. Palladium sensitization (as opposed to no sensitization to both metals) associated with exposure to dental crowns [odds ratio (OR) 2.0], skin reactivity to metals (OR 2.8), oral lichenoid lesions (OR 4.7), xerostomia (OR 7.3), and metal taste (OR 20.7), but not with eczema, stomatitis, or oral burning sensation. Additionally, xerostomia (OR 8.7) and metal taste (OR 4.6) associated with sensitization to both metals

Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: U-Hg	NA	Overall mean U-Hg concentration varied between 0.12 µg Hg/L and 0.31 µg Hg/L or 0.13 µg Hg/g Cr and 0.40 µg Hg/g Cr. Females higher mean U-Hg levels vs men. Overall 95th %ile: 2.95 µg Hg/L, the 99th %ile 7.34E µg Hg/L, and 99.9th %ile 17.45 µg Hg/L. Expressed as µg Hg/g Cr, overall 95th %ile 2.57 µg Hg/g Cr, 99th %ile 5.65 µg Hg/g Cr, and 99.9th %iles 12.14 µg Hg/g Cr. Overall, 98.2% participants U-Hg levels below 7 µg Hg/L and 97.7% U-Hg levels below 5 µg Hg/g Cr. All data estimates for Canadian population
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Urine/blood concentrations: As, Hg, Tl, Sb, Cd, Ni, Cr, Co, V, and Mn	NA	Amalgam dental fillings and contact lenses associated with Hg levels
Y: Amalgam; composites; ceramics; NA	Allergies/Oral health: Adverse symptoms in oral mucosa (contact stomatitis, OLL, contact dermatitis, OLP, leukoplakia); subjective symptoms (e.g. moth burning, inflammation)	4yrs of data collection (2012-16)	86 subjects (83.7% women and 16.3% men) with oral symptoms of contact allergy. Most common allergies were metals, Ni and Co most common allergens. Many allergies indicated to ingredients of cosmetics and composites. Allergies to components in methacrylate-containing denture resins ranked at 5. 52.4% patients showed mucosal changes. Contact stomatitis (54.5%) and OLL (20.5%) most frequently diagnosed. 86% patients reported subjective complaints. Pain and burning sensations in mouth were mostly reported
Borderline: Amalgam; NA	Auditory/Exposure: MeHg from maternal or childhood fish consumption and Hg° from maternal or childhood amalgam. Associations with Hg exposure and auditory outcomes	9yrs	Hg exposures similar for both sexes. 7/210 evaluable participants had either a mild (5) or moderate (2) hearing loss. Four mild monaural hearing loss and 3 either mild (1) or moderate (2) bilateral hearing loss. No participant > than moderate hearing loss in either ear. Hg exposures higher in participants with either a mild or moderate hearing loss, but differences were not SS. Among 210 with complete data, neither prenatal nor postnatal MeHg nor Hg° exposure statistically significantly associated with any of ABR endpoints (p>0.05 for all 72 associations). Neither prenatal nor postnatal Hg° exposure was associated with any of the OAE endpoints (p>0.05). MeHg exposure statistically associated with 6/56 DPOAE endpoints (p-values between 0.0001 and 0.023), but none of 40 CEOAE endpoints. Two associations occurred with prenatal MeHg exposures and 1 of those beneficial effect. 4 of other associations occurred with postnatal MeHg exposures with 2 found in left ears of both males and females and other 2 in left and right ear of females (n=1 each)
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Cord blood Hg concentrations as biomarker of Hg exposure, Maternal blood specimen	NA	Median Hg concentrations: 0.63 mg/l (range 0.14–2.9 mg/l) and 0.80 mg/l (range 0.15–2.54 mg/l) for maternal and cord blood, respectively. No cord blood Hg concentrations reached hazardous level for neurodevelopmental effects in children exposed to Hg in utero (EPA reference dose for Hg of 5.8 mg/l in cord blood). Strong positive correlation between maternal and cord blood Hg levels (r=0.79; Po0.001). Cord blood Hg significantly associated with no.maternal amalgam fillings (r=0.46, P=0.001) and no.yrs since last filling (r=0.37, P=0.001); associations remained significant after adjustment for maternal age/ducation. DA fillings in girls and women of reproductive age should be used with caution, to avoid increased prenatal Hg exposure

N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Urine, hair, blood Hg		Mean (geometric) Hg levels hair (hHg), blood (bHg), urine (uHg), and average estimated Hg intake from fish: 0.62 mg/g, 3.75 mg/L, 1.32 mg/L, and 0.12 mg/kg body weight/day, respectively. Out of 88 SNPs successfully genotyped, Hg biomarker levels differed by genotype for 25 SNPs, one of which remained significant following Bonferroni correction in ANOVA. When associations between sources of Hg exposure and SNPs analyzed with respect to Hg biomarker concentrations, 38 SNPs significant main effects and/or gene-Hg exposure source interactions. 25, 23, and four SNPs showed significant main effects and/or interactions for hHg, bHg, and uHg levels, respectively (p=0.05), and six SNPs (in GCLC, MT1M, MT4, ATP7B, and BDNF) significant following Bonferroni correction
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: U-Hg	NA	Mean±SD of U-Hg concentrations of exposure vs nonexposure groups: 1.50±1.78 µg/g creatinine and 0.53±0.63 µg/g creatinine, respectively. Exposure group significantly higher levels vs onexposure group (p<0.01). U-Hg concentration significantly increased with increase no.teeth filled with amalgam, cavity surfaces involved, and no.defective amalgam fillings, and latest exposure time (p<0.001). Multiple regression analysis of amalgam-related factors and U-Hg concentrations post correction for confounding factors, U-Hg concentration in group with six or more amalgam-filled teeth, 11 or more cavity surfaces, and two or more defective amalgams significantly higher than nonexposure group (p<0.001)
Y Half and half: Amalgam; NA	Neurological: Compared Hg exposures from seafood and amalgam fillings in 401 ALS and 452 non-ALS respondents	NA	ALS and non-ALS respondents did not differ in frequency seafood consumption or monthly Hg intake from favourite seafoods. Both groups similar numbers of current/former Hg fillings. No evidence Hg exposure from eating seafood or Hg dental fillings with ALS risk
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood levels: Cd, Pb, Hg	NA	Between European cities, B-Pb and B-Cd results vary little (range of geometric means: 13.5–27.0 µg/l and 0.25–0.65 µg/l, respectively); variation of B-Hg larger (0.40–1.38 µg/l). Between non-European cities results for B-Pb, B-Cd and B-Hg: 19.2–68.0, 0.39–0.99 and 1.01–2.73 µg/l, respectively. Smoking SS determinant for B-Cd, fish and shellfish intakes contributed to B-Hg and B-Pb, amalgam fillings contributed to B-Hg

Y: Amalgam ; Without amalgam	Immune function/Exposure: Patch testing (n =21) for dental series and did lymphocyte transformation test (n =18) for metals; Hg in samples of blood (n =19), urine (n =19), saliva (n =20), and scalp hair (n =17)	NA	Prevalence metal immune hypersensitivity in 26 patients: 92.3%. Elevations Hg occurred 81.2 % (26/32). Mean (±SD) Hg blood concentrations: 7.6 ± 13.6 g/L; mean in urine: 1.9 ± 2.5 g/L; mean scalp hair: 2.2 ± 2.5 g/g; mean saliva: 38.1 ± 52.1 g/L. Subgroup analyses: Hg elevation associated with Hg amalgams in patients with MCS (22 patients) vs controls (8 patients) (odds ratio 11 : 95 % confidence interval 1.5 to 81.6; μ =0.023) ^{μ} P
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: DC exposure level: Cd, Hg, OC pesticides and PCBs	NA	Median U-Hg and Cd: 0.81 µg/l and < 0.5 µg/l respectively. Hg levels higher in participants having min. 3 DAs, and consuming sea fish > 1/wk. Although Hg levels in most participants lower than some health-based guidelines, higher than neighboring countries where ban or restrictions on DAs use implemented. U-Cd levels in current smokers significantly higher than former/smokers, as well as non-smokers for passively exposed vs non-exposed ones. Median PCB-153 and -180 serum levels: 53.8 and 41.1 ng/g lipid respectively, PCB-138 below limit of quantification of 0.15 µg/l in 49% of samples
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Urinary Cd, hair Hg	NA	Geometric mean levels for hair Hg: 0.383 µg/g and 0.204 µg/g for respectively mothers and children. Urinary-Cd in mother's and children's detected at geometric mean concentration of respectively 0.21 and 0.04 µg/l. For both biomarkers, levels measured in mothers and their child correlated. While urinary Cd levels increased with age, no trend found for hair Hg content, except mothers levels > children. Hair Hg content increased significantly with no.DA fillings, explaining partially higher levels in mothers by their higher presence rate of amalgams vs children. Fish/seafood consumption other main parameter determining hair-Hg. No relationship between smoking status and Cd or Hg levels, but few smokers in study . Urinary Cd levels higher in mothers and children in urban areas, for Hg significant difference only for children
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood Pb, Cd, and Hg	NA	Geometric means: 21.5 µg/l (95% CI 20-23) blood Pb, 0.67 µg/l (95% CI 0.56-0.79) blood Cd, and 0.75 µg/l (95% CI 0.64-0.87) blood total Hg. Regression analyses: increased blood Pb significantly associated with BMI values < 25 kg/m ² , being postmenopausal, smoking habits, use of non-electrical/central heating sources , and frequent or constant trucks passing through residential area. Blood Cd significantly higher in smokers and decreased as education increased. Fish consumption and no.teeth containing amalgam the only significant factors related to blood Hg

N: Amalgam; NA	Allergy: Allergy dental metals	CT	28/206 patients positive patch test reactions to metals used in dentistry. No positive patch test reactions highest for gold sodium thiosulfate, palladium chloride, and Ni sulfate (n=¼ 10, respectively), followed by amalgam, ammoniated Hg, and Co chloride (n=4, respectively) and amalgam-mixed metals (including Cu, tin, Zn, and S1), and ammonium tetrachloroplatinate (n=1). Only 14 (7%)/ 206 patients had clinically relevant contact allergy with conditions of oral mucosa (n=7 with lichen planus and n=7 with stomatitis) and positive patch test reactions to dental metals containing suspected allergen. Symptom improvement in one patient with amalgam contact allergy 2 weeks after removal of dental fillings
N: (Meth)acrylates; NA	Allergy: Positive patch test results (meth)acrylates	7yrs (patch-tested and followed up)	Among 2263 patch tested patients, 122 underwent aimed testing with an extended (meth)acrylate series, 37 showed positive and relevant reactions. 25 cases (67.6%) occupational. Hand eczema with pulpitis observed in 32 patients. 28 related to artificial nails, 3 related to dental materials, 2 were industrial workers. Oral lesions associated with dental prostheses were in 4 patients. 31 patients reacted to >1 (meth)acrylate. Beauty technicians working with artificial nails most affected group (80% occupational cases)
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Urinary Hg	NA	Based on CHMS data, 17.7 million Canadians aged ≥6yrs collectively carry 191.1 million amalgam surfaces, representing 76.4 million amalgam-restored teeth. Average Hg exposures : Children—0.065 µg Hg/kg/day; Teens—0.032 µg/kg-day; Adults—0.033 µg/kg-day; and Seniors—0.041 µg/kg/day. Of Canadians with DA restorations, 80.4% experience daily dose of Hg that exceeds Canadian REL-associated dose. No amalgam surfaces that will not result in exceeding the REL-associated dose varied from 2 amalgam surfaces (children, both sexes) to 7 surfaces (adult males)
Y: Amalgam; Non amalgam	Auditory: Auditory thresholds 0.25 to 16 kHz	NA	No significant correlation (p=.05) between composite (non-amalgam) filling or drilling data and auditory thresholds. Significant positive linear correlation between amalgam filling data and auditory thresholds at 8, 11.2, 12.5, 14, and 16 kHz. Strongest association (r0.587, n39, pB.001, r2 0.345) at 14 kHz, where each additional amalgam filling associated with 2.4 dB decline in hearing threshold (95% confidence interval [CI], 1.33.5 dB). Indicate association between more amalgam fillings and poorer thresholds at higher frequencies, which could contribute to presbycusis in developed countries
Y: Amalgam ; NA	Exposure: Hair Hg	NA	Hair-Hg in subjects with multiple amalgam fillings significantly higher vs no amalgam fillings+ correlated with no. amalgam fillings in following regression equation: log Hg=0.084 amalgam fillings + 3.377 (r=0.339, p=0.003). Multiple regressio: hair-Hg significantly correlated with amalgam fillings (r=0.292; p=0.014) and age (r=0.284; p=0.017) but not significantly with BMI (r=0.060). Regression equation of log Hg=0.071 amalgam fillings + 0.011 age + 0.006 BMI + 2.72 was obtained (r=0.447), with 0.200 of determination coefficient

Y-half and half: Amalgam; None	Genotoxicity/Exposure: Hg and Se concentrations in maternal hair and blood/serum, placenta and cord blood/serum; MT2 concentrations and MT2A-5A/G (rs28366003) polymorphism	NA	Hg and Se in maternal hair and blood/serum, placenta and cord blood/serum positively associated with fish consumption, highest values in coastal subjects. Concentrations of each element and between elements correlated across matrices. Increasing no.amalgams correlated linearly with increased Hg levels in maternal and cord serum and was not associated with serum MT2. No association MT2A-5A/G polymorphism and Hg or Se levels. Higher fish consumption in coastal vs. continental Croatia and increases of both Hg and Se related to fish consumption in all analyzed samples. Increased blood Hg reflected predominant MeHg share from seafood, while increased serum Hg matched exposure from DA
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Urinary concentrations 14 trace elements (As, Cd, Co, chromium, Cu, Hg, Mn, molybdenum, Ni, lead, antimony, selenium, thallium, and Zn) and their exposure determinants	Cohort study initiated in 1991–1992; reassessed in 2019	Young adults: increased toxic element concentrations, children: higher concentrations essential elements. Hg concentrations associated with no.DA filling and seafood intake; As concentrations associated with seafood, rice, and mushroom consumption. Mushroom consumption influenced Pb concentrations. Sex differences for Cd, Zn, Ni, and Co. Between 17.9% and 25% participants exceeded recommended GV for As, 2.4% to 2.8% exceeded GV for Cd. 1 participant exceeded GV for Hg, none exceeded GVs for chromium and thallium. Essential trace elements' GVs surpassed by 38% to 68.5% participants for Zn, 1.3% to 1.8% for molybdenum, and 0.2% to 0.3% for selenium
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Hg isotope ratios in hair/urine; survey detailing demographic characteristics, occupational practices (e.g., no.amalgams handled/wk), no.personal DAs, and fish consumption patterns	NA	Hair from North American dental professionals high positive $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ values (mean=1.86‰, 1 SD=0.12‰, n=11). Thus, in people regularly consuming fish, total Hg concentrations in hair reflect exposure to MeHg. Urine from same people: range $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ values (0.29 to 1.77‰, 2 SD=0.06‰, n=12) significantly correlated to no.DAs. Hypothesize fish-derived MeHg is demethylated within body, causing mass dependent fractionation and excretion of inorganic Hg in urine. Urinary Hg represents mixture demethylated fish-derived MeHg and amalgam-derived inorganic Hg. Estimate majority (>70%) U-Hg from individuals with <10 DAs derived from MeHg in fish. Data suggest that within populations that consume fish, urine total Hg concentrations may overestimate Hg exposure from personal DAs
Y: Amalgam; NA	Neuropsych/Exposure: Neuropsychological domains: psychomotor speed, attention, and verbal and visual long-term memory, free thyroxin, thyroidea stimulating hormone (TSH), alanine transaminase, cobolamin, folate, and serum creatinine, U-Hg.	NA	Only SS relationship: U-Hg values and visual long-term memory, where urine values explained 30%variability. Study low statistical power and other methodological limitations: interpret results with caution. Neuropsychological findings indicative of subsequent cognitive injuries difficult to find in groups of otherwise healthy dental personnel with previous occupational Hg exposure

Y: Borderline: Amalgam ; NA	Neuropsych: Hg cord blood, child neurodevelopment at 18 months (cognitive, language, motor scales)	Pregnancy, delivery and up to 18 months post-partum?	Negative association between low-to-moderate Hg exposure in children with normal neurodevelopmental outcome and cognitive and fine motor scores at 18 months of age as assessed by Bayley III. Hg-related decrease in cognitive score observed only in children carrying at least one Apoe ε4 allele, while the decrease in fine motor scores was independent of the Apoegenotype. Cord blood total Hg levels gave a positive correlation with frequency of fish consumption during pregnancy (rs=0.45, p=0.001), but did not correlate with no.dental amalgam fillings in mothers (rs=0.08, p=0.224)
N: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Venous blood (women 16 mL, men 23 mL), spot urine (50 mL), 3 cm of scalp hair close to the scalp from occipital area (1 g) and women a maximum of 80 mL of breast milk	Milk collected multiple feeds max. 6 days)	Essential elements showed no significant deficiencies or excessive levels in study population, largely determined by sex and/or the participating women's physiological status (postpartum, lactation), and dietary sources. Toxic elements' levels mainly below harmful levels. Lifestyle and nutritional habits significant determinants of exposure to Cd (smoking and game meat consumption), Hg (seafood and amalgam fillings), As (seafood) and Pb (alcohol consumption, smoking, game meat consumption and type of water supply). Geographical pattern confirmed, due to past mining activities combined with naturally elevated background levels in cases of Pb (Mežica Valley), Hg (Idrija and Posočje) and As exposure (Zasavje). Increased seafood consumption in coastal study area: higher Hg and As (arsenobetaine) levels
Y: Amalgam; No fillings	Oral health	NA	10 % (868) reporting problems from dental filling materials. Clear differences between two groups, having problems vs not. Group reporting problems from dental filling materials perceived general and oral health as worse vs others. More frequently they asked questions about adverse effects from dental filling materials, had changed dental fillings and crowns, and had amalgam present. They also felt less well treated by dental personnel and were not so pleased with dental care in general as others
N: Amalgam ; Healthy adults	Allergy: Delayed type hypersensitivity	NA	Main source metal exposure dental metal restorations. Majority patients (87%) had positive lymphocyte reaction to min.1 metal and 63% reacted to two or more metals tested. Within control group, 43% healthy subjects reacted to 1 metal and 18% reacted to two or more metals. Increased metal reactivity in patient group compared vs control group SS (p<0.0001). Most frequent allergens: Ni, Hg, gold and palladium
N: Amalgam; NA	MSK/Allergy: Patients' health, metal allergy	5yr; 10 yr	All FM patients tested positive to min.1 metals tested. Most frequent reactions: Ni, inorganic Hg, Cd and Pb. Some healthy controls responded to inorganic Hg in vitro but most tests negative. Examination 5yrs later showed 50% patients no longer fulfilled FM diagnosis, 20% improved and remaining 30% still had FM. All patients reported subjective health improvement, correlating with normalisation of metal-specific responses in vitro
Y: Amalgam; No fillings	Neuropsych: Alzheimer's disease	NA	Individuals exposed to amalgam fillings higher risk of Alzheimer's disease (OR=1.105, 95 %, CI=1.025-1.190) vs non-exposed. OR Alzheimer's disease 1.07 (95 % CI=0.962-1.196) in men and 1.132 (95% CI=1.022-1.254) in women. Women exposed to amalgam fillings 1.132 times more likely to have Alzheimer's disease vs non-exposed counterparts

Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: U-Hg	NA	Widespread exposure to Hg in individual exposure scores and U-Hg . For most respondents level of Hg exposure low. Use of Cu amalgam, which is heated before it is applied, particular concern as a significant source of Hg exposure in dental personnel
Y: Amalgam; No RLS	Multiple health: Diagnosis/severity RLS; mental status and physical efficiency; Physical disability; QOL; overall actual health state	NA	Subjects with RLS: significantly higher no.amalgam dental fillings vs subjects without RLS symptoms. Presence of other metal dental restorative materials and no. amalgam dental fillings reported in past no significant influence on RLS symptoms
Y: Assumed amalgam ; NA	Multiple health: Long term symptoms and social consequences of symptoms. Local symptoms: burning mouth, dry mouth, taste disturbances, and TMJ pain, while general symptoms could include pain from muscles and joints, fatigue, headache, and vertigo	NR	Patients with complex symptoms at baseline had worse prognosis (i.e. more symptoms remaining) at follow-up than patients with local symptoms only. Replacement of dental materials seemed to have largest impact on alleviation of symptoms reported. Those with remaining complex symptoms had more often stopped working or had decreased their work hours because of symptoms. Only one-sixth of the patients symptom-free at follow-up. Results indicate relationship between patients with complex symptoms and social consequences in daily life
Y: Resin- based materials ; NA	Allergy: Symptoms and signs of reactions	Reactions occurring in three year period-1996-9. During dental treatment, within 24 hrs, a week and after 18 months	Majority symptoms intra-oral or combination of intra- and extra-oral symptoms that appeared within first 24 hr after treatment. Most common adverse effects reported: skin problems, oral ulcers, burning mouth. Within <1wk reactions disappeared in 50% of patients
N : amalgam; NA	Allergy: Patch test reactions	NR	96 OLP patients and 152 cheilitis patients patch tested during the 15-year period. 71 (73.9%) OLP patients and 100 (65.8%) cheilitis patients recorded one or more relevant reactions. 43(44.8%), 22 (22.9%), 21 (21.9%) and 17 (17.7%) OLP patients had relevant reactions to Hg-related chemicals, amalgam, spearmint and carvone, respectively, vs 6 (3.9%), 3 (2.0%), 4 (2.6%) and 0 (0%) cheilitis patients, respectively (p-value <0.001 each). 4 (4.2%) OLP patients had relevant positive reactions to sodium metabisulfite, vs none in cheilitis group (p-value 0.021)
N: Amalgam ; NA	Allergy: Patch test reactions	NA	Allergen: amalgam; n of patients tested: 198; reactions, %: 2.0 (positive) and 75.0 (relevant)

<p>Y half and half alongside seafood consumption: Amalgams; NA</p>	<p>Exposure: No.DAs, maternal hair/infant meconium Hg</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>Median THg concentration in meconium: 11.1 (range: 0.41–375.2) ng/g and inorganic Hg (Hg₂) presented 98.8% (range: 82%–100%, CV: 2%) of THg. Significant correlation between meconium and MH Hg levels. Highest correlation between hair THg and meconium MeHg. Correlation analysis including MB (available only for Croatian population): Significant positive correlation between THg in meconium and THg in MB (RS=0.642). Additionally, MeHg from MB was correlated with MeHg in meconium (Rs=0.898), while the correlation between Hg₂ in MB and meconium was positive, but not significant. Maternal seafood intake significantly correlated with meconium MeHg (Rs=0.498) and Hg₂ (Rs=0.201). Multiple linear regression: (performed on the Slovenian population, N=143) confirmed a positive association between meconium MeHg and seafood intake. Furthermore, meconium Hg₂ positively associated with no.maternal DA fillings, but linear regression models did not confirm correlation between seafood intake and meconium Hg₂ levels. Assume Hg₀ released from maternal DA fillings and MeHg from seafood intake both transported through placental barrier and portioned between different foetal compartments including meconium. Weak correlation between maternal seafood intake and Hg₂ levels in meconium suggests evidence of MeHg demethylation. However, because correlation not confirmed by multiple regression, MeHg demethylation during prenatal life cannot be confirmed nor excluded</p>
<p>Y: Amalgam; NA</p>	<p>Exposure: U-Hg</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>No statistically significant differences found in geometric mean of U-Hg concentrations between the study and control groups (GM±SD, 0.44±0.440 and 0.5±0.270 µg/g creatinine, respectively, p=0.242). Among different factors affecting Hg exposure in dental surgeries, only duration of dental practice showed SS influence on total Hg-U (r=0.3000; p=0.024). Subjects- two groups, with vs without amalgam fillings, SS difference in U-Hg concentrations (0.60 ± 0.720, n=38; 0.36 ± 0.650, n=29; p=0.004) between groups</p>
<p>N (one of a number e.g. chronic fatigue syndrome): Amalgam; NA</p>	<p>Health other: Self-reported amalgam poisoning</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>909 respondents (response rate=88.8%), 863 complete data. 39.6% patients considered they may suffer from one or more unexplained conditions. Concerns strongly and positively associated with recent symptom load and no.life stressors. If burnout and food intolerance excluded, corresponding associations found</p>
<p>Y: Amalgam; Control (10) non occupational exposure</p>	<p>Exposure: Levels of Hg in urine and hair</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>Current dental exposures based on most recent findings do not exceed acceptable risk levels and are below biological limit of Hg in urine valid for occupationally exposed persons (100 µg.g⁻¹ of creatinine), median value was 1.48 (min. < limit of detection (LOD), max. 17.14) µg.g⁻¹ of creatinine (40 persons), total Hg content in hair of dental personnel expressed as median value: 0.340 (min. 0.060, max.1.628) µg.g⁻¹. In controls (10 persons) was total Hg content in urine expressed as median value 0.36 (min. < LOD, max. 2.74) µg.g⁻¹ of creatinine, in hair was median value 0.224 (min. 0.059, max. 0.453) µg.g⁻¹</p>

N: Amalgam; NA	Endocrine/Exposure: Hg levels in blood and thyroid gland hormone concentrations in serum (both mothers and children)	NR	Median THg and MeHg levels in maternal blood, cord blood, and blood of 6-month-old children were 0.50, 0.53, and 0.32 and 0.22, 0.32, and 0.08 µg/L, respectively. Significant correlations between paired maternal–cord blood levels for THg and MeHg, with a greater transplacental transport of MeHg compared with THg (mean cord/maternal blood ratio, 1.80 vs. 1.24). Maternal blood THg Better predictor of TSH levels in children than their current THg exposure. Positive correlation between maternal THg and children’s TSH. T3 and fT3 levels in children negatively related to cord blood THg in majority (Caucasian) subgroup, whereas these associations positive in Roma subgroup. Mothers with DA fillings significantly lower T4 and fT4 levels. Moreover, fT4 in mothers of boys negatively correlated with maternal THg levels. MeHg exposure lowered T3 levels in the mothers of girls. Results suggest low-level Hg exposure can affect thyroid hormone status during prenatal and early postnatal exposure depending on form of Hg, gender, ethnicity, lifestyle, or socioeconomic status (DA fillings)
Y: Monomers and additives-resin-based; NA	Exposure: Compounds in saliva	Before restoration, up to 24 hrs post restoration	Leaching of monomers and degradation products was highest within 30min after restoration placement. Highest median concentrations monomers: UDMA, BisEMA-3, and TEGDMA; besides BisEMA-3 and TEGDMA, no monomersdetected after 24 h. Mono- and demethacrylated degradation products present up to 24 h and concentrations generally higher vs monomers. In patients with multiple restorations, degradation products still present in sample taken before next operation, several weeks after previous operation
Y: Amalgams and composite resin-based fillings; NA	Genotoxicity: Cytogenetic damage (MN test) and DNA damage (comet assay) in oral mucosa cells	NR	The results obtained show that both amalgams and resin-based composite fillings can induce genotoxic damage in human oral mucosa cells, as convincingly and dose-dependently inferred from the results of the MN test and, more marginally, from comet assay data. Lifestyle variables, also including alcohol intake and smoking habits, did not affect the genotoxic response and did not act as confounding factors. Thus, we provide unequivocal evidence for the genotoxicity of both amalgams and resin-based dental fillings in humans not only by testing circulating lymphocytes but also by analyzing oral mucosa cells. These findings are of particular relevance due to the circumstance that subjects with restorative materials are exposed continuously and for long periods of time.
N (alongside lead, Cd etc): Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Blood/urinary Hg	NR	Average internal exposure (geometric means) in blood: 9.47 µg/L for Pb and below 0.06 µg/L (limit of quantification) for Cd, and in urine 0.072 µg/L for Cd, 0.067 µg/L for Hg, and 0.393 µg/L for chromium. Younger children higher concentrations of Pb and chromium vs 14-17 year-old adolescents, boys slightly higher Hg concentrations than girls. Higher Pb concentrations in participants with domestic fuel and in non smoking children with smokers in household, higher levels Cd associated with smoking and vegetarian diet and higher levels Hg with consumption of seafood and amalgam teeth fillings. No specific exposure determinants for chromium. Health based guidance value HBM-I not exceeded for Hg. For U-Cd iexceeded by 0.6% of study population. None of exceedances related to substantial tobacco smoke exposure

N (alongside lead and calcium): Amalgam;	Exposure: Hg concentration breast milk	NR	Median breast milk concentrations (minimum-maximum): 0.20 µg Hg/kg (b0.058–0.89), 0.057 µg Cd/kg (0.017–1.2), and b0.67 µg Pb/kg (0.2–7.5). Cd no significant relation with any exposure variable investigated. Pb associated with intake of liver and kidneys from game. Breast milk Hg : no. amalgam fillings and high fish consumption significant predictors (p=0.001). Significant association (p=0.01) between breast milk Hg and maternal consumption of Atlantic halibut, lean fish, mussels and scallops and lifetime consumption of crab. Seafood intake alone=10% variance, and with amalgam explained 46% of variance in breast milk Hg
N: Amalgam; NA	Other: Urinary porphyrin concentrations	NR	Elevated copro- (p < 0.009), hexacarboxyl- (p < 0.01) and pentacarboxyl- (p < 0.001) porphyrin concentrations significantly associated with AU but not with PDD-NOS. No differences found between NT and AU in urinary Hg levels or in past Hg exposure as determined by fish consumption, number of dental amalgam fillings, or vaccines received.
Y: Amalgam vs CR	Exposure: urinary mercury	7yrs	Mean urinary mercury concentrations in amalgam group increased to peak of ~ 3.2 µg/L at yr2 and then declined to baseline levels by yr7 follow-up. Strong, positive association between U-Hg, both no. amalgam surfaces and time since placement. Girls significantly higher mean urinary mercury concentrations than boys throughout amalgam treatment. No differences by race in urinary mercury concentration associated with amalgam exposure
Y: Amalgam; NA	Exposure: Endogenous MeHg exposure-Hg, Hgin and MeHg levels-Hg, methylHg, inorganic bound Hg	NR	Significantly higher level inorganic bound Hg (Hgin) found in hair of dentists. No. amalgam fillings had slightly significant effect on Hgin; fish consumption significant influence on MeHg and slightly on Hgin. Other parameters not significant
Y: Amalgams handled in workplace; NA	CVD/Exposure: Total Hg levels in hair and blood samples analyzed as indicators of methylHg exposure and in urine as indicator of primarily elemental Hg exposure. SBP, DBP and lipid profiles (total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol [HDL], low-density lipoprotein cholesterol [LDL] and triglycerides)	NR	Geometric means (geometric standard deviations) for blood, hair, and U-Hg were 3.64 (2.39) µg/L, 0.60 (2.91) µg/g, and 1.30 (2.44) µg/L, respectively. For every one µg/L increase in specific gravity-adjusted U-Hg, LDL increased by 2.31 mg/dL (95% CI=0.09, 4.54), in linear regression adjusting for BMI, race, sex, polyunsaturated fatty acid intake from fish consumption, smoking status, and use of cholesterol-lowering medication. No significant associations between Hg biomarkers and blood pressure or hair or blood Hg with lipid levels observed. Results suggest that elemental Hg exposure may influence LDL concentrations in adults with low-level exposure

Y Borderline: Amalgam; Exposure level	Exposure: Blood THg, IHg, and MeHg and to urine creatinine corrected Hg (UTHg)	NR	Subjects grouped into three groups (0) those without AMG (64.4%), (1) those with 1–5 dental AMG restorations (19.7%), (2) those with > 5 AMG (16%). Seafood consumption increased total U-Hg and THg and MeHg in blood, but unlike AMG, seafood did not increase blood IHg. Strong correlation blood (THg and IHg) and urine (UTHg) levels with no.AMGs. In subpopulation without fish consumption, having >5 AMG restorations raised blood THg (103%), IHg (221%), and urine UTHg (221%) over group without AMG. Subjects < 6yrs old with >5 AMG restorations had highest blood IHg and urine UTHg among all age groups. Elevation of bivalent IHg on a large scale in children warrants urgent in-depth risk assessment with specific attention to genetic- and gender-associated vulnerabilities
Y: Amalgam and bisphenol A (BPA) from composite resin; Exposure level	Exposure: Blood THg, IHg, and MeHg and to urine creatinine corrected Hg (UTHg)	NR	Blood THg and IHg in 2003–2004 were significantly higher in the subjects with DSR (geometric mean of 0.48, 0.69 and 1.17 µg/l for THg; 0.32, 0.33 and 0.39 µg/l for IHg with DSR 0, 1–8 and 48). Similarly, increases of THg, IHg and MeHg also observed in 2013–2014 (geometric mean of 0.51, 0.69 and 0.99 µg/l for THg; 0.40, 0.49 and 0.66 µg/l for MeHg; 0.20, 0.22 and 0.29 µg/l for IHg with DSR 0, 1–8 and 48). Blood THg and IHg in 2003–2004 and THg, IHg and MeHg in 2011– 2012 associated with no.DSRs. Decrease in urinary BPA from 2003 to 2004–2011–2012 observed, but no significant increase with DSRs in either period of study
Y: Amalgam ; NA	Visual/ocular: Ocular accidents	NA	Ocular accidents reported by 73% participants. Amalgam and NaOCl were foreign bodies most frequently associated with ocular accidents. Medical assistance sought in 16% of recent accidents. No permanent eye damage reported. Regular use of magnification (OR:0.305, 95% CI:0.123–0.754) and yrs clinical experience (OR:0.191, 95%CI:0.066–0.551) significant predictors for incidence of ocular accidents. Adequate eye protection utilized by 82% of endodontists. Endodontists with eyesight deficiencies attended ocular examination more frequently (p=0.018)
Y: Amalgam tattoos; NA	Oral health: Tissue reactions to amalgam tattoos	NA	17 oral ATs (amalgam tattoos) examined by transmission electron microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis. Ultrastructurally, in ATs, three kinds of electron-dense particles observed. Largest particles ranged in size from 0.5 up to several 100 nm. Smaller electron-dense inclusions (0.5–0.1 µm) seen extracellularly associated with meshworks of elastic fibers and collagen bundles. Third and smallest type of particles (5–30nm in diameter) found with basement membranes of small vessels and pericytes and particularly decorating collagen bundles. Element analysis regularly revealed presence of silver, sulphur, Cu and lead in the AT decay products. Hg found in only one instance. Tissue reactions due to AT minimal. No acute inflammatory changes seen. Larger inclusions occasionally surrounded by macrophages and multinucleated cells. TEM and element analysis specific cases be helpful in the differential diagnosis of pigmented lesions of the oral mucosa

usted Odds Ratio, As=Arsenic, ASD=Autism Spectrum Disorder, AT=Amalgam Tattoo's, AU=Autism, Be=Beryllium, Bis-EMA=Ethoxylated bisphenol-A dimethacrylate, bis-GMA=2,2-Bis[4-(2-Hydroxy[1]3-ium, CD=Celiac Disease, CDC=Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, CEOAE=Click Evoked Otoacoustic Emissions, CHMS=The Canadian Health Measures Survey, CI=Confidence Interval, P=Diastolic Blood Pressure, DD=Male Dentists, DDE=Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene, DEGDA=Diethyleneglycol Diacrylate, DPOAE=Distortion Product and Click Evoked Otoacoustic Emissions, rsitivity, EM=Electromagnetic, EMA=Ethyl Methacrylate, EPA=Environmental Protection Agency, Fe=Iron, FLEHS=Flemish Biomonitoring Programmes, FM=Fibromyalgia, FSH=Follicle-Stimulating Hormone, fl=European Human Biomonitoring Initiative, HCB=Hexachlorobenzene, HCP=Health Care Professionals, Hg=Mercury, Hgin=Inorganic bound Mercury, HI=Health Impact, HQ=Hazard Quotient, HR=Hazard itivity, MeHg=Methylmercury, MG= α 1-microglobulin, MH=Maternal Hair, MMA=Methylmethacrylate, Mn=Manganese, MN=Micronucleus Test, MS=Multiple Sclerosis, MT2=Maternal Serum Metallothionein, l, NS=Not specified, NSS=Not Statistically Significant, NYC=New York City, OCD=Occupational Contact Dermatitis, OH=Overhang, OLL=Oral Lichenoid Lesions, OLP=Oral Lichen Planus, OR=Odds Ratio, dontal Status, Pt=Platinum, PTB=Pre-Term Birth, QOL=Quality of Life, Rb=Rubidium, RCT=Randomized Controlled Trial, REL=Recommended Exposure Levels, Rh=Rhodium, RLS=Restless Legs Syndrome, lobulin, S-Hg=Serum Hg, Si=Silicone, Sn=Tin, SNP=Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms, SS=Statistical Significance, T3=Triiodothyronine, T4=Thyroxine, TBHg= Total Blood Hg, TD=Typically Developing, itanium, Tl=Thallium, TMJ= Temporomandibular Joint, TPH=Urethane-modified bisGMA-based composite, TREGDMA=Triethyleneglycol Diacrylate, TS=Tooth Surface, TSH=Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone,